

A Fundamental Model for Constructing the Physical Universe*

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Abstract

In this paper we develop a model for physics that allows us to *derive* basic things that are typically assumed as given, including ordinary space and time, and their properties.

We start with a simple argument for what the primitive *element* and the primitive *structure* for the universe should be, and summarize the results as four postulates. In section 3 we use those postulates to derive a (3+1)-dimensional structure, interpreted as ordinary space and time.

In section 4 we derive two uniform scalar energy fields, the first of which initially drives a rapid expansion of space (i.e. it acts as an inflaton field), but afterwards manifests as a cosmological constant (i.e. dark energy). We interpret one branch of the second scalar field to be the Higgs field.

The fourth postulate is a generator of *independence relations*, and so it is a generator of fundamental *symmetries*. We show that many symmetries or uniformities of the physical universe can be derived by simply applying postulate 4. These include the uniformity (isotropy and homogeneity) of ordinary space, the uniform distribution of dark energy, the uniform distribution of energy in the primordial volume of space (and thus in the cosmic microwave background), and the (default) uniform smearing of particle locations across space (in quantum mechanics).

Of course, a new type of model such as this is going to involve a learning curve. But most of the new concepts and terminology are introduced by the end of section 2. After that, we just keep applying them.

Keywords: Cosmology; scalar fields; dark energy; Higgs field; fundamental symmetries; independence relations; ontological priority; quantum measurement

*Before reading this article, it is recommended to read the much shorter “[New Fundamental Principles for Physics](#)” (4 pages).

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1 Introduction

Many important systems are based on a primitive *element* and a primitive *structure*. In biological systems, for example, the primitive element is the nucleotide molecule, and the primitive structure is a *sequence* of nucleotides (e.g. a codon, or a gene). Likewise, for computer systems (i.e. digital electronics) the primitive element is the bit, and the primitive structure is a sequence of bits (e.g. an 8-bit byte). And in natural language the primitive element is the letter or phoneme, and the primitive structure is a sequence of letters or phonemes (e.g. a word or a sentence).

Such systems must have a way of translating or computing the primitive elements and structures into meaningful output. In biology this is accomplished by the operations of ribosomes, enzymes, etc., acting on the nucleotide strings. For computers, the operations of logic gates on the bit strings perform this function. And in natural language the operations of lexical analysis, parsing, and context translate a string of letters/phonemes into meaning.

It may also be that the *physical universe* itself is based on this same type of model. If so, then the following questions become paramount: (i) What is the primitive element for the universe?, (ii) what is the primitive structure?, and (iii) how are these elements and structures translated (or computed) into the meaningful output that we call the physical universe? The following reasoning suggests answers for questions (i) and (ii).

Consider two states, A and B , where B is the state that we find ourselves in right now, in which all of the things of the universe exist (i.e. space, time, particles, forces, dark energy, etc.); and A is the beginning state, ontologically *prior* to B , in which *none* of those things exist.

We note that “ A is *ontologically prior* to B ” means that [1]:

A is (existentially) *independent* of B , whereas B is (existentially) *dependent* on A . (Alternatively, we may convey the same meaning by saying that “ B is ontologically *subsequent* to A ”.)

Thus the creation of B does not (and cannot) affect A ; i.e., A still exists, and is unchanged. This is in contrast to a more conventional notion in which the beginning state A (whatever it might be) is tacitly relegated to mere *temporal* priority – so that the temporally subsequent existence of B supplants or replaces A , or at least A becomes irrelevant or ignorable once B is created (e.g., the big-bang temporal-evolution model seems to evoke such a scenario). In the present model, A 's *ontological* priority means that it *stays* operant and relevant (this will be elaborated in section 2).

So, starting with state A , something presumably happens to create state B . To estimate what that something is, we ask the following question: In the simplest possible terms, what is the basic *difference* between states A and B ? Answer: In some sense, state B is *displaced* from state A ; for, if B were *not* displaced from A , then B would be the *same* as A , and none of the stuff of the known universe would exist. This leads to the following simple idea: The primitive element for creating the physical universe is *displacement from a prior state*.

Now, just as you can't get much from a single bit, or a single nucleotide molecule, or a single letter/phoneme, so also you probably can't get much from a *single* displacement from a prior state. This suggests that the basic paradigm for creating the universe (i.e., the method for creating state B , starting from state A) is a *sequence* of displacements from prior states. Such a sequence of displacements will yield a sequence of *states*, any two of which will have the ordering relation that one is *prior*, and the other is *subsequent*. To reflect the ordering in this sequence of fundamental states, we will usually refer to the states as *levels*.

We thus arrive at the following two postulates:

1. The primitive element for creating the physical universe is a type of *displacement*. Specifically: *displacement from a prior level*.
2. The primitive structure is a *sequence* of such displacements.

With respect to the first postulate, we may refer to both displacements and levels as “elements” (or *basic* elements) of the system, but will reserve the term “primitive element” for the displacements alone.

We note that these displacements have a *direction* associated with them: they point from a prior level to a subsequent level (as will become more clear in section 2). This leads us to think of the displacements as *vectors*. Furthermore, just as with the states A and B , we assume that any two displacements or levels in the sequence have the relation that one is ontologically prior, and the other is ontologically subsequent; thus, independence and dependence relations hold between them. These considerations suggest two more postulates:

3. Each displacement is a *one-dimensional vector*, constituting a *different*, but related, one-dimensional space. (The basic relations between these displacements/vectors are stated in the next postulate.)
4. Prior things (e.g. displacements, levels, and constructions from them) are *independent of* subsequent things; and, conversely, subsequent things are *dependent on* prior things. (As previously indicated, the terms “prior” and “subsequent” denote here *ontological* relations, *not* temporal relations. See the definition of “ontological priority” given above; and also see [1] for a more detailed explication.)

Some disambiguation is needed at this point. In mechanics, a “displacement” is a vector within *existing* 3-dimensional space, i.e. within ordinary space. In the present model, however, we *do not* take ordinary space as pre-existing; in fact, using the postulates above, we will *derive* 3-dimensional ordinary space and its properties (section 3). We thus take the postulated displacements as one-dimensional entities in themselves, without thinking of them as occurring within an existing space.

It may be noted that the primitive element and primitive structure for the universe (as postulated above) are analogous to those of digital electronics, where either a finite or zero

displacement from a lower voltage level constitutes a “1” or a “0”, respectively, yielding a *bit*; and a sequence of eight such displacements constitutes a *byte*. And, just as the operations of a digital computer can thus be considered “a *calculus* of displacements from a lower voltage level”, so also the present model for constructing the physical universe can be considered “a calculus of displacements from prior levels”. In the case of digital computers, the calculus involves the operations of logic gates on the voltage displacements. In the present model, the calculus involves (the operations of) the dependence and independence *relations* between the displacements, as per postulate 4. Thus, if we allow that the postulated displacements represent a new kind of “bit”, then the present model qualifies as “It from bit” [2].

What is displaced? In section 4, it will be assumed that *energy* is displaced from one level to another. However, in the first three sections we will focus on *logical* aspects of the displacements and their relations with one another, and the *geometrical* consequences.

Of course, a viable model for constructing the physical universe should offer answers to fundamental questions, such as: What is the origin of ordinary, three-dimensional space? What is dark energy, and what prevents there from being a huge amount of it? Why does the presence of energy affect space and time? Why is the speed of light absolute, whereas other speeds are relative? Why are particle locations (e.g. in quantum mechanics) smeared across space by default? And, what factors are involved in “collapsing” the default smeared state into a definite position?

Indeed, using the four postulates above (and two more that will be stated later), we develop a model for the basic construction of the physical universe – including the construction of ordinary space and time, a quantum of action, fundamental particles and interactions, inflation, dark energy, etc. As development of the model progresses, the essential role of “observers” in the construction process becomes more and more clear. With respect to question (iii) above, it will be shown that a method for translating a sequence of displacements into physical meaning is by taking into account *relations* between the displacements – specifically, their dependence and independence relations (i.e. postulate 4). In particular, such relations will allow us to derive a (3+1)-dimensional structure which, in the context of the model, is best interpreted as the ordinary space and time dimensions of our experience. Moreover, the symmetry properties of ordinary space and time (e.g. spatial isotropy and homogeneity) also follow from such relations; that is, since postulate 4 is a generator of “independence relations”, then it is also a generator of fundamental symmetries.

The model developed herein may be referred to as “system P”, and the world so constructed from it as “world P”. The choice of the letter “P” reflects the presumption that world P corresponds to the **p**hysical universe.

2 Displacements, levels, and relations: the structure and basic properties of the model

To construct our model for the physical universe, we must begin with a state at which the things of the universe do not exist (otherwise our construction would be circular), i.e. a state

that is absent the elementary particles, forces, and even space and time. We will call this state *level 0*. We do not, however, presume that level 0 is a state of nothingness, or that nothing exists at level 0. We merely claim that nothing that constitutes the known universe exists at level 0; for level 0 is by definition a *state* that is immediately *prior* to the construction of the physical universe. (Level 0 thus corresponds to state *A* in the introduction.)

Recalling our first three postulates, we say that a displacement from level 0, to be denoted as \mathbf{d}_0 , generates a *new* state, which we call *level 1*. Likewise, a displacement from level 1, denoted as \mathbf{d}_1 , generates another new state, which we call *level 2*. And a displacement from level 2, denoted as \mathbf{d}_2 , yields *level 3*; and so on. So, in general, \mathbf{d}_k represents a displacement from level k that generates level $k + 1$ (for $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots$); thus, relative to each other, level k is *prior*, and levels $k + 1, k + 2$, etc., are *subsequent*; also, relative to each other, \mathbf{d}_k is prior, and $\mathbf{d}_{k+1}, \mathbf{d}_{k+2}$, etc., are subsequent. (Again, the terms “prior” and “subsequent” refer to ontological – not temporal – priority and subsequence.)

In Fig. 1, where levels are represented by horizontal lines, and displacements are represented by vertical arrows from a prior level to the next subsequent level, we illustrate the construction of levels 1 through 4 via displacements \mathbf{d}_0 through \mathbf{d}_3 . To the right of each level in Fig. 1 is shown the sequence of displacements that is required to construct that level (the round brackets indicate a sequence, as is common in mathematics). Thus, the sequences of displacements that are needed to create levels 0, 1, 2, and 3 are $()$, (\mathbf{d}_0) , $(\mathbf{d}_0, \mathbf{d}_1)$, and $(\mathbf{d}_0, \mathbf{d}_1, \mathbf{d}_2)$, respectively; and the sequence $(\mathbf{d}_0, \mathbf{d}_1, \mathbf{d}_2, \mathbf{d}_3)$ constructs all of the levels (above level 0) in Fig. 1. (Note that displacements \mathbf{d}_0 through \mathbf{d}_3 , and levels 0 through 4, will be sufficient for our purposes in this paper.)

Fig. 1: Construction of levels 1 through 4 via the displacement sequence $(\mathbf{d}_0, \mathbf{d}_1, \mathbf{d}_2, \mathbf{d}_3)$. The displacement sequence that is required to construct a given level is shown to the right of that level.

As just described, the *order* of construction starts with level 0 at the bottom of Fig. 1 and proceeds in the upward direction. Thus, level 0 is prior to all other elements (levels or displacements), and subsequent to none; \mathbf{d}_0 is subsequent to level 0, but prior to level 1, \mathbf{d}_1 , level 2, etc.; and so on. So, in general, a given element x is subsequent to everything below it in Fig. 1, but prior to everything above it. By postulate 4, this means that element x

is *dependent* on everything below it in the Figure, but *independent* of everything above it. Thus, for example, level 0 is independent of all other elements, and dependent on none.

Since level 0 is our *starting point* (or *starting state*) for constructing the system, then we must say that it is a *nonconstructed* element of that system, whereas the subsequent displacements and levels (\mathbf{d}_0 , level 1, \mathbf{d}_1 , level 2, etc.) are *constructed* elements of the system. So anything subsequent to level 0 is a *constructed* entity of the system.

2.1 The scope, nesting, and inheritance rules

Let x be a thing of the system (e.g. x is a level, a set of one or more displacements, or something constructed from them). Wherever x is **in effect** or **operant** is called the **scope** of x . Wherever x is *not* operant is *outside* the scope of x .

By postulate 4, things that are *subsequent* to x are (ontologically) *dependent* on x , and thus within the scope of x . Conversely, things that are *prior* to x are *independent* of x , and thus outside the scope of x . All of this is summarized in what will be called the basic **scope rule**, stated as follows:

A given thing in the system is in effect/operant at (i.e. contains within its scope) those things that are *subsequent*, but is not in effect at (does not contain within its scope) those things that are *prior*.

From this we deduce a corollary to the basic scope rule:

A given *element* in the system (i.e. a displacement or level) is in effect/operant at (contains within its scope) those elements that are *above* it in Fig. 1, and is not operant at (does not contain within its scope) those elements that are *below* it in Fig. 1.

Thus, for example, \mathbf{d}_0 is operant at level 1 and above, but is *not* operant at level 0 (i.e., level 1 and above are within the scope of \mathbf{d}_0 , but level 0 is not). Level 0, on the other hand, is prior to every other thing in the system, so it is in effect/operant at all of those other things; i.e., all of those other things are within the scope of level 0 (thus we might say that level 0 has system-wide or universal scope). We may refer to the basic scope rule or the above corollary as simply “the scope rule”.

Since \mathbf{d}_k is *not* in effect at level k , but *is* in effect at level $k + 1$, then level $k + 1$ represents the *state* at which the displacement \mathbf{d}_k first comes into effect; by the scope rule, \mathbf{d}_k then *stays* in effect for all subsequent levels. Thus, the displacement \mathbf{d}_0 first comes into effect at level 1, and stays in effect for levels 2, 3, and 4; likewise, \mathbf{d}_1 first comes into effect at level 2, and stays in effect for levels 3 and 4. Let us say that the level at which a displacement first comes into effect is its *native level*. Thus, level 1 is the native level for \mathbf{d}_0 ; level 2 is the native level for \mathbf{d}_1 ; and so on. That is, the native level for \mathbf{d}_k is level $k + 1$. Moreover, the concept of native level can be extended to things that are *constructed from* displacements; thus, for example, something that is constructed using \mathbf{d}_0 and \mathbf{d}_1 (and no other displacements) is

native to level 2, since those two displacements are first *jointly* in effect at that level. We note also that the displacements that are in effect/operant at a given level are the *same* as the ones that are required to *construct* that level (as described earlier, and as listed in the sequences to the right of each level in Fig. 1).

Another corollary to the scope rule is called the **nesting rule**, as follows:

Subsequent things (e.g. levels, displacements, and any constructions derived from them) are ontologically **nested** (and thus embedded, contained, encapsulated, confined) *within* the scope of prior things; and, conversely, prior things contain, encapsulate and confine (within their scope) subsequent things.

Thus the nesting rule may also be called the *confinement* rule.

In constructing the fundamental sequence of displacements ($\mathbf{d}_0, \mathbf{d}_1, \mathbf{d}_2, \mathbf{d}_3$), since any displacements that are in effect at level k are also in effect at the subsequent level $k + 1$, then we can think of the latter level as *inheriting* all of the displacements that are in effect at the former level. And since this is true of displacements, then it is also true of anything that is associated with or constructed from them. This aspect of the system – whereby, in constructing the said sequence, things that are created at one level (or, if you will, *generation*) are passed on to the next subsequent level (and thus, by extension, to *all* subsequent levels) – will be called the **inheritance rule**.

Since the sequence of displacements ($\mathbf{d}_0, \mathbf{d}_1, \mathbf{d}_2, \mathbf{d}_3$) springs from level 0, then we can say that level 0 is the *origin* of the system. And since, by the nesting/confinement rule, all of the constructed elements/entities/things of that system are logically nested/confined within level 0, then we can also say that level 0 is the *boundary* of the system. Thus, level 0 is both the origin *and* boundary of the system. So, in that sense, although level 0 is a necessary part of its ontology, it is not technically *within* the world that is constructed by the system. Furthermore, since the present system is a model for constructing the physical universe, then we have shown that, according to this model: (a) The *origin* and *boundary* of the physical universe are the *same* thing (which we call level 0); and (b) the origin/boundary of the universe is a fundamental, ontological *state* – not a spatiotemporal *place*. This result is therefore a first step in liberating our minds from the problematic influence of spatiotemporal imagery (e.g., in big-bang-style evolution) when attempting to suss out the *fundamental* construction process for the universe; and it is a first step in shifting our minds toward an *ontological* model of this process. As we will see, ontological relations dictate geometry, not the other way around.

Finally, when a set of things in the system (i.e. elements, or things constructed from them) is arranged in a list from prior to subsequent, then we will say that those things are arranged in their *order of priority*. If a thing is neither prior nor subsequent to another thing, then we say that they are *of the same order*, or *coordinate*.

3 Constructing spaces

Following postulate 3, let us model each displacement as a one-dimensional *vector*; i.e. we model each \mathbf{d}_k ($k = 0, 1, 2, 3$) as a one-dimensional vector going from level k to level $k + 1$. Thus, \mathbf{d}_0 is a one-dimensional vector from level 0 to level 1; \mathbf{d}_1 is a one-dimensional vector from level 1 to level 2; and so on. These vectors are represented graphically by the vertical arrows in Fig. 1.

Moreover, each \mathbf{d}_k constitutes a *different* one-dimensional space. Although they are different in this respect, the \mathbf{d}_k are nevertheless *related* by the dependence and independence relations that have been postulated and discussed.

3.1 Constructing a (3+1)-dimensional structure at level 2

Since \mathbf{d}_0 is the only displacement in effect at level 1, and since (by postulate 3) it is *one* dimensional, then it is fair to say that the four postulates construct a system that is *one dimensional* at level 1.

Since both \mathbf{d}_0 and \mathbf{d}_1 are in effect at level 2, and since each of these constitutes a different one-dimensional space, then it might seem – at first consideration – that the system should be *two* dimensional at level 2. But a different picture emerges once we take into account the *relations* between \mathbf{d}_0 and \mathbf{d}_1 , as follows.

Recall from postulate 4 that \mathbf{d}_0 is independent of \mathbf{d}_1 , and that this relation is *asymmetric* – i.e. \mathbf{d}_1 is *dependent* on \mathbf{d}_0 . Since \mathbf{d}_0 and \mathbf{d}_1 are linear entities (i.e. one-dimensional vectors), we interpret that these relations imply a kind of (asymmetric) *linear* independence, with the following property: the vector \mathbf{d}_0 may have a component along the line of \mathbf{d}_1 , and is also free to have a component *perpendicular/orthogonal* (i.e. at 90 degrees) to \mathbf{d}_1 . But, by symmetry, the perpendicular component can be anywhere in a two-dimensional *plane* orthogonal to \mathbf{d}_1 . The two dimensions of this orthogonal plane, plus the one dimension along the line of \mathbf{d}_1 , makes three dimensions. Thus, from the perspective of \mathbf{d}_1 , the vector \mathbf{d}_0 has *three* dimensions; i.e., \mathbf{d}_0 constitutes a *three-dimensional* space. We might say, therefore, that the view of \mathbf{d}_0 from the perspective of \mathbf{d}_1 “bootstraps” the former from a one-dimensional vector into a three-dimensional space.

In summary, to construct its interpretation of \mathbf{d}_0 , we can think of \mathbf{d}_1 as applying postulates 3 and 4 in succession: first, by postulate 3, \mathbf{d}_0 is a one-dimensional vector; second, by postulate 4, \mathbf{d}_0 is independent of \mathbf{d}_1 – which allows the former to have a component that is orthogonal to \mathbf{d}_1 , with the result that \mathbf{d}_1 sees \mathbf{d}_0 as three dimensional.

Conversely, we can ask, how does \mathbf{d}_1 “look” from the perspective of \mathbf{d}_0 ? Since \mathbf{d}_1 is *not* independent of \mathbf{d}_0 , then the former is *not* free to have a component that is orthogonal to the latter, and so \mathbf{d}_0 sees \mathbf{d}_1 strictly as per postulate 3: as a *one-dimensional* vector. This view of \mathbf{d}_1 – from the perspective of \mathbf{d}_0 – first comes into effect at level 2 (since \mathbf{d}_1 itself is native to that level).

So, at level 2 we have the three dimensions of \mathbf{d}_0 , plus the one dimension of \mathbf{d}_1 , for a total of *four* dimensions. Since this system is a model for constructing the physical universe, we

interpret that the three dimensions of \mathbf{d}_0 are just the three dimensions of *ordinary space*, and the one dimension of \mathbf{d}_1 is the dimension of *time*; thereby yielding at level 2 the signature 3+1 space and time dimensions of our experience. The dimension of time, therefore, being a consequence of \mathbf{d}_1 (and \mathbf{d}_0), does not exist at levels 0 and 1, but only comes into existence at level 2; likewise, since ordinary, three-dimensional space is a consequence of \mathbf{d}_0 and \mathbf{d}_1 , it also does not exist at levels 0 and 1, but only comes into existence at level 2.

Note that, although \mathbf{d}_0 itself is independent of \mathbf{d}_1 , the triple dimensionality of \mathbf{d}_0 at level 2 is *not* independent of \mathbf{d}_1 . That is, in the process described above, \mathbf{d}_0 only manifests as *three* dimensional when it is related to, or juxtaposed with, \mathbf{d}_1 . Thus, the triple dimensionality of \mathbf{d}_0 at level 2 (i.e. the triple dimensionality of ordinary space) is in fact *dependent* on \mathbf{d}_1 . As a corollary, the construction of ordinary space is dependent on *both* \mathbf{d}_0 and \mathbf{d}_1 ; so both of those displacements are prior to, and thus independent of, ordinary space.

We have shown, among other things, that \mathbf{d}_0 manifests differently at levels 1 and 2. At level 1 it is *one* dimensional. But when juxtaposed with \mathbf{d}_1 at level 2 it manifests as a *three*-dimensional space. Note that \mathbf{d}_0 itself does not change from level to level: it represents a displacement from level 0 to level 1 wherever it appears (i.e. wherever it is in effect). This is analogous to, e.g., the A, G, C and T nucleotides in biology, which are always the same molecules wherever they appear, but yield a different output (i.e. amino acid or protein) depending on what other nucleotides/letters they are juxtaposed with in a sequence. In other words, like the “letters” in a DNA sequence, the *meaning* of \mathbf{d}_0 is context dependent; which is just what we might expect for an element of a *language*, thus supporting the notion promulgated by many that the basis for the physical universe might be, to some degree at least, informational or computational in nature (e.g. [2–4]).

We might say that level 2 has *two* dimensions as *input* (one for \mathbf{d}_0 , plus one for \mathbf{d}_1), but has *four* dimensions as *output* – three for \mathbf{d}_0 , and one for \mathbf{d}_1 . Which brings us back to question (iii) in the introduction: How are the primitive elements of the model (which at level 2 are the inputs \mathbf{d}_0 and \mathbf{d}_1) translated (or, if you will, *computed*) into the meaningful output that we call the physical universe? We now see that at least a partial answer is that the *relations* between prior and subsequent elements are what translate them into meaningful output. In the present case, the independence relation between \mathbf{d}_0 and \mathbf{d}_1 at level 2 translates/transforms the manifestation of the former from a one-dimensional entity into a three-dimensional space.

We can thus say that the construction of each space at level 2 requires the participation of an *observer*, in the sense that \mathbf{d}_1 “observing” \mathbf{d}_0 constructs ordinary, three-dimensional space, and \mathbf{d}_0 “observing” \mathbf{d}_1 constructs one-dimensional time. With ordinary space *itself* constructed by an observation of sorts, it becomes more plausible that, e.g., the *position* of an object *within* ordinary space might also be constructed by some type of observation, as seems to be the case in quantum mechanics (more about that in section 5).

We have just described how the spaces and dimensionalities at level 2 are constructed. Now we will do the same for levels 3 and 4.

3.2 The spaces of levels 3 and 4

By the scope rule, \mathbf{d}_0 and \mathbf{d}_1 are operant at levels 3 and 4, just as they are at level 2. And the *relations between* \mathbf{d}_0 and \mathbf{d}_1 also hold at levels 3 and 4, the same as they do at level 2 (i.e. \mathbf{d}_0 is independent of \mathbf{d}_1 , but not the converse). So, at levels 3 and 4 – as at level 2 – \mathbf{d}_0 will appear to \mathbf{d}_1 as a three-dimensional space (i.e. ordinary space), and \mathbf{d}_1 will appear to \mathbf{d}_0 as a one-dimensional space (i.e. time). In other words, the spaces that are constructed at level 2 are also operant and manifest at levels 3 and 4. In summary, ordinary space and time are constructed and operant (i.e. exist) *at level 2 and above*; that is, ordinary space and time are *native* to level 2.

Let us denote ordinary, three-dimensional space as S_{01}^3 , where the superscript indicates the number of dimensions, and the 0 followed by 1 in the subscript indicates that this is the space of \mathbf{d}_0 as seen by \mathbf{d}_1 . Likewise, let us denote time as S_{10}^1 , where, again, the superscript indicates the dimension of this space, and the 1 followed by 0 in the subscript indicates that this is the space of \mathbf{d}_1 as seen by \mathbf{d}_0 .

Now let us focus on level 3, where the displacements \mathbf{d}_0 , \mathbf{d}_1 , and \mathbf{d}_2 are in effect. We start by discussing the relations between \mathbf{d}_0 and \mathbf{d}_2 at that level. The former is independent of the latter, so \mathbf{d}_0 is *three* dimensional from the viewpoint of \mathbf{d}_2 . We thus have the generation of a *new* three-dimensional space at level 3, which we denote as S_{02}^3 . Likewise, \mathbf{d}_1 is independent of \mathbf{d}_2 ; so the latter will see \mathbf{d}_1 as three dimensional (whereas, as already stated, \mathbf{d}_1 has only one dimension from the viewpoint of \mathbf{d}_0). This yields yet another three-dimensional space at level 3, which we denote as S_{12}^3 . In addition, at level 3 we also have the *one*-dimensional space, S_{20}^1 , of \mathbf{d}_2 as seen by \mathbf{d}_0 ; and the one-dimensional space, S_{21}^1 , of \mathbf{d}_2 as seen by \mathbf{d}_1 . We note that all of these new spaces depend on \mathbf{d}_2 , so they are only operant (and only manifest) at level 3 and above; furthermore, they are subsequent to ordinary space, S_{01}^3 , and so (by the nesting rule) they are ontologically *nested* within it.

We now ask, *where* are the three-dimensional spaces located relative to each other? The three-dimensional spaces operant at level 3 have the order of priority $S_{01}^3, S_{02}^3, S_{12}^3$;¹ so, by the nesting rule, S_{12}^3 is (ontologically) nested/contained/confined within S_{02}^3 , which in turn is nested/confined within S_{01}^3 (ordinary space); or, to put it another way, S_{01}^3 (ordinary space) contains S_{02}^3 , which in turn contains S_{12}^3 . More will be said about the nested/confined spaces of level 3 in section 4, where we construct the *particles* of the system.

Now let us move up to level 4. The displacements \mathbf{d}_0 , \mathbf{d}_1 , and \mathbf{d}_2 are still in effect at level 4, so the spaces of level 3 also exist at level 4. In addition, the displacement \mathbf{d}_3 is in effect at level 4, so the relationship between it and the prior displacements \mathbf{d}_x ($x = 0, 1, 2$) generates three new, three-dimensional spaces, which we denote collectively as S_{x3}^3 ; and we note that these spaces will be internal to, or nested within, S_{12}^3 . Lastly, there are the three new, one-dimensional spaces of: \mathbf{d}_3 as seen by \mathbf{d}_0 , denoted as S_{30}^1 ; \mathbf{d}_3 as seen by \mathbf{d}_1 , denoted as S_{31}^1 ; and \mathbf{d}_3 as seen by \mathbf{d}_2 , denoted as S_{32}^1 – which may be denoted collectively as S_{3y}^1 .

¹Obviously, S_{01}^3 (ordinary space) is prior to the other two, since it is native to level 2, whereas the others are native to level 3. We assume that S_{02}^3 is prior to S_{12}^3 since the former is a manifestation, or mode, of \mathbf{d}_0 , whereas the latter is a mode of \mathbf{d}_1 (and the former displacement is prior to the latter).

($y = 0, 1, 2$).² These new spaces at level 4 are nested/confined within S_{12}^3 , which is nested within ordinary space, S_{01}^3 .

Note that most of the spaces constructed above are mentioned just for completeness. In the rest of the paper, we will mainly be concerned with the arena of ordinary space and time, and a little bit concerned with the extra/confined spaces that are native to level 3.

In summary: The view of \mathbf{d}_0 from the perspective of \mathbf{d}_1 is native to level 2, and thus yields ordinary 3-dimensional space at level 2 and above; likewise, the view of \mathbf{d}_1 from the perspective of \mathbf{d}_0 is also native to level 2, and thus yields the single time dimension at level 2 and above. At level 3 and above, other spaces come into play which are ontologically subsequent to (and thus nested/confined within) ordinary space and time.

3.3 The number of dimensions at levels 2, 3, and 4

From the results above, the spaces that are in effect/operant/manifest at level 2 comprise the *four*-dimensional set

$$\{S_{10}^1, S_{01}^3\}, \quad (1)$$

and the spaces at level 3 comprise the *twelve*-dimensional set

$$\{S_{10}^1, S_{01}^3, S_{20}^1, S_{21}^1, S_{02}^3, S_{12}^3\}, \quad (2)$$

and the spaces at level 4 comprise the *twenty-four*-dimensional set

$$\{S_{10}^1, S_{01}^3, S_{20}^1, S_{21}^1, S_{02}^3, S_{12}^3, S_{3y}^1, S_{x3}^3\}, \quad (3)$$

where $x, y = 0, 1, 2$. As already mentioned, the 8 extra dimensions at level 3, and the 20 extra dimensions at level 4 are nested/confined within ordinary space. In sections 4.4.7 and 4.4.8 we will conclude, moreover, that these extra dimensions are also *compactified* within ordinary space.

The dimensionalities of the system thus bear some similarity to those of string theory [5, 6]. Does this suggest that the displacements of the system have some relation to *strings*? Possibly – but we will not specifically expand on the string idea any further in this paper.

3.4 The uniformity of ordinary space

Recall that ordinary, three-dimensional space is created when \mathbf{d}_0 is viewed from the perspective of \mathbf{d}_1 .

Since \mathbf{d}_0 is native to level 1, but ordinary space is native to level 2, then it follows that (a) \mathbf{d}_0 is *prior to* ordinary space, and thus (b) \mathbf{d}_0 is *independent of* ordinary space (by postulate 4). (This argument for \mathbf{d}_0 's independence from ordinary space is in addition to the one already given in section 3.1.)

²Note that, for a space S_{xy}^z , the superscript, z , is actually *redundant* information, since it is always equal to 3 if $x < y$, and is equal to 1 if $x > y$.

Suppose now that the process of \mathbf{d}_1 viewing \mathbf{d}_0 constructs an ordinary space that is *nonuniform* – i.e., it is either anisotropic or inhomogeneous, or both. Such nonuniformity would mean that \mathbf{d}_0 is manifesting (in this process) as a *variable function of* ordinary space (e.g., having a particular position or direction). Hence \mathbf{d}_0 would be functionally *dependent on* ordinary space – thereby contradicting (b) above. We thus conclude that, as constructed, ordinary space must be perfectly uniform, i.e. perfectly *isotropic* and *homogeneous*.

In addition, the construction of ordinary space cannot result in \mathbf{d}_0 manifesting as a *vector*, or *vector field*, within that space; for, if it did, then \mathbf{d}_0 would be functionally dependent on ordinary space, which would again contradict (b). Given that *vector* fields have been ruled out, it seems we have little choice but to assume that \mathbf{d}_0 manifests in this process as a uniform *scalar* field – *uniform*, because any *nonuniformity* would make the manifestation of \mathbf{d}_0 functionally dependent on ordinary space, which would, again, violate/contradict its independence from that space. Since, in this process, \mathbf{d}_0 *is* ordinary space, then the uniform scalar field for \mathbf{d}_0 is just ordinary space itself, and/or the energy associated with it (to be elaborated in section 4.4.1).

3.5 Ordinary/classical time

Since \mathbf{d}_0 is prior to \mathbf{d}_1 , then we will assume that \mathbf{d}_0 's view of \mathbf{d}_1 (which constructs 1-dimensional *time*) is prior to \mathbf{d}_1 's view of \mathbf{d}_0 (which constructs ordinary, 3-dimensional space). It then follows that the time dimension (as constructed) is prior to, and thus independent of, ordinary space. Given this independence, it also follows (by the same reasoning used in section 3.4) that the time dimension must manifest *uniformly* throughout ordinary space; i.e., it must operate the *same* everywhere in space. (For, if it *did not* operate the same everywhere, it would be functionally dependent on ordinary space, and thereby yield a contradiction.)

Moreover, recall that \mathbf{d}_0 sees \mathbf{d}_1 as a one-dimensional *vector* (section 3.1), thereby *preserving* the directionality of \mathbf{d}_1 in this process. We interpret that this directional aspect of \mathbf{d}_1 (with respect to \mathbf{d}_0) is the source of time's "arrow". However, if this arrow/directionality of time were to manifest as a particular direction in ordinary space, it would again make the time dimension functionally dependent on ordinary space, and thereby yield a contradiction; thus, the directional aspect of \mathbf{d}_1 (with respect to \mathbf{d}_0), i.e. the arrow of time, is not married to any particular direction in ordinary space (as comports with observation/experience).

We therefore interpret that \mathbf{d}_0 's view of \mathbf{d}_1 produces what might be called *ordinary* or *classical* time – e.g., time as the independent variable in classical mechanics (which does indeed manifest and operate the same everywhere in space).

The *modification* of time (intervals) that occurs in special relativity is due to the absoluteness of the speed of light, which we derive in section 5.3. The modification of time due to gravity is accounted for in section 6.

In summary, we found in section 3.4 that the process of constructing ordinary space "washes out" the directionality (i.e. vectorial nature) of \mathbf{d}_0 , leaving it to manifest as a scalar field. In the present section, however, we concluded that a different process (namely, the view of \mathbf{d}_1 from the perspective of \mathbf{d}_0 , which yields time) *preserves* \mathbf{d}_1 's directionality, yielding the

arrow of time. Likewise, it will be argued much later (in section 5) that additional processes that involve the viewing of \mathbf{d}_0 and \mathbf{d}_1 (namely, from the perspective of *level 0*) also preserve directionality in those displacements – yielding relative position, relative velocity, and spin vectors.

3.6 Symmetries

We have shown above that basic symmetries/uniformities can be derived from underlying *independence relations*. The present model, however, allows us to take this a step deeper: In postulate 4, independence relations themselves are generated by *relations of ontological priority*. It is thus suggested that many (possibly *all*) elementary symmetries of the physical universe should be traceable/reducible to relations of ontological priority that are instances of postulate 4.

Indeed, we concluded in section 3.4 that the uniformity of ordinary space (i.e., its isotropy, homogeneity, and scalar/non-directional nature) is attributable to the ontological priority of \mathbf{d}_0 to that space. Thus, the standard (i.e. Noether [7]) reductions of conservation of linear and angular momentum to the symmetries of spatial homogeneity and isotropy, respectively, are further reduced by the present model to that (more fundamental) relation of ontological priority. Likewise, as just concluded in section 3.5, the spatial uniformity of ordinary/classical time stems from time’s ontological priority to space.

In addition, we will see later (in sections 4.8 and 4.4.1) that the (default) uniform smearing across space of particle locations in quantum mechanics, and the (likely) uniform nature of dark energy, are other symmetries that can be attributed to relations of ontological priority that are instances of postulate 4 (actually, these symmetries will be attributed to the *same* relation of ontological priority discussed above: \mathbf{d}_0 ’s ontological priority to ordinary space).

In summary, instead of having a hundred fundamental symmetries emanating from (potentially) a hundred different sources, postulate 4 offers to be a *unified* generator of all such symmetries.

3.7 Rapid expansion of ordinary space within the first instant of time

Recall that \mathbf{d}_0 at level 1 is *one* dimensional – having, let us say, a length of d_0 . The time dimension, being a result of \mathbf{d}_1 , does not exist at this level/stage. Given that a one-dimensional object has *zero* volume, then the physical universe at this stage of development has a volume of zero.

Since the time dimension comes into existence with the displacement \mathbf{d}_1 , then the *advent* of \mathbf{d}_1 defines the time $t = 0$, at which point d_0 has the value $d_0(t = 0)$, which may be denoted as $d_{0,0}$. So, at exactly $t = 0$, or within the first instant after it, the existence/perspective of \mathbf{d}_1 causes \mathbf{d}_0 to manifest as the *three*-dimensional space S_{01}^3 , with a volume on the order of $d_{0,0}^3$. Thus the volume of S_{01}^3 (ordinary space) goes from zero to around $d_{0,0}^3$ within a time interval of zero, or near-zero, length – which constitutes a potentially very large, perhaps

infinite, rate of spatial expansion. I propose, therefore, that this rapid spatial expansion, triggered by the advent of \mathbf{d}_1 at $t = 0$, is the process known as *inflation* [8, 9].

Note that, under the above mechanism, inflation has a natural beginning: the advent of \mathbf{d}_1 at $t = 0$. And it also has a natural *ending*: it ends when the volume of ordinary space is around $d_{0,0}^3$. So inflation only lasts for the time (if any) that it takes for the *one*-dimensional space of length $d_{0,0}$ to become the *three*-dimensional space of approximate volume $d_{0,0}^3$.

4 Constructing fields and particles

4.1 Basic energy considerations

In constructing the fundamental sequence $(\mathbf{d}_0, \mathbf{d}_1, \mathbf{d}_2, \mathbf{d}_3)$, let us assume that *energy* is needed to create each of the displacements \mathbf{d}_k ($k = 0, 1, 2, 3$). We can think of this energy as being stored along the length of \mathbf{d}_k , and/or as being stored in the level $(k + 1)$ that is created by \mathbf{d}_k . We will use the term “ \mathbf{d}_k energy” to denote the energy of the displacement \mathbf{d}_k .

The displacement \mathbf{d}_0 , then, is a *process* through which \mathbf{d}_0 energy is input into level 1; likewise, \mathbf{d}_1 is a process that inputs \mathbf{d}_1 energy into level 2; \mathbf{d}_2 is a process that places \mathbf{d}_2 energy into level 3; and so on. We assume that all of these energies are nonzero and positive. So the energy of the system, due to contributions from the sources mentioned, is positive.

4.2 Aspects of energy flow and identity

In terms of energy *flow*, the construction of the sequence $(\mathbf{d}_0, \mathbf{d}_1, \mathbf{d}_2, \mathbf{d}_3)$ proceeds as follows:

- First, the \mathbf{d}_0 displacement/process inputs “ \mathbf{d}_0 energy” into level 1.
- Next, the \mathbf{d}_1 process displaces some energy from level 1 up to level 2, as “ \mathbf{d}_1 energy” (it is *not* \mathbf{d}_0 energy at this point).
- Then the \mathbf{d}_2 process takes some energy from level 2 and displaces it up to level 3, as “ \mathbf{d}_2 energy” (it is *not* \mathbf{d}_1 energy at this point).
- Finally, the \mathbf{d}_3 process takes some of the energy at level 3 and displaces it up to level 4, as “ \mathbf{d}_3 energy”.

Additionally, the inheritance rule seems to require that we keep track of the *provenance* of energy in the system. For this purpose, we will use the term “ E_j energy” ($j = 1, 2, 3, 4$), where the subscript indicates the level (j) into which the energy is placed. Unlike the designation “ \mathbf{d}_k energy”, the designation “ E_j energy” is an *inheritable* property, and has to do with energy *identities* and/or *types* that survive displacement to higher levels. In constructing the sequence $(\mathbf{d}_0, \mathbf{d}_1, \mathbf{d}_2, \mathbf{d}_3)$, it works as follows:

- First, the displacement \mathbf{d}_0 inputs \mathbf{d}_0 energy into level 1; this energy has the identity/type that we call “ E_1 energy”.

- Next, some of the E_1 energy at level 1 is displaced (via \mathbf{d}_1) up to level 2, thereby making it both “ \mathbf{d}_1 energy” and “ E_2 energy” – but, due to its provenance (and the inheritance rule), still also retaining its essential identity as E_1 energy.
- Some of the E_2 energy at level 2 is then displaced (via \mathbf{d}_2) up to level 3, thereby making it both “ \mathbf{d}_2 energy” and “ E_3 energy” – but, due to its provenance (and the inheritance rule), still also retaining its prior identities as E_1 energy and E_2 energy.
- And similarly for the \mathbf{d}_3 process, with corresponding “ \mathbf{d}_3 energy” and “ E_4 energy” at level 4 – still also retaining the prior identities of E_1 energy, E_2 energy, and E_3 energy.

It follows that, in constructing the fundamental sequence $(\mathbf{d}_0, \mathbf{d}_1, \mathbf{d}_2, \mathbf{d}_3)$, E_j energy is also E_{j-1} energy, E_{j-2} energy, \dots , E_1 energy. Thus, *all* of these E_j energies are essentially also “ E_1 energy”. Moreover, *all* of the needed energy for constructing this sequence *enters* the system via the displacement \mathbf{d}_0 , and thus begins its life in the system as E_1 energy at level 1. Its essential identity as “ E_1 energy” is retained, even as it is displaced up to subsequent levels and becomes also E_2 energy, E_3 energy, etc.

In summary, the term “ \mathbf{d}_k energy” ($k = 0, 1, 2, 3$) informs us about the *process* by which energy is placed into level $k + 1$ when constructing the sequence $(\mathbf{d}_0, \mathbf{d}_1, \mathbf{d}_2, \mathbf{d}_3)$. The designation “ E_j energy”, on the other hand, is a kind of brand identity that energy receives/acquires when it enters level j , which then survives subsequent displacement to higher levels. Thus, the set of E_j energies possessed by a given *quantity* of energy keeps track of the provenance of that energy in entering the system, as well as the levels (if any) that it was subsequently displaced up to. So, for example, if a given quantity of energy is said to possess the energy types E_1 , E_2 , and E_3 , then we know that it entered the system at level 1 (via \mathbf{d}_0), and was subsequently displaced up to level 3.

Everyone is familiar with the standard types of energy in physics: kinetic, potential, and rest energies. In the present model, however, the E_j -energy types ($j = 1, 2, 3, 4$) are considered to be more fundamental (moreover, it will be shown that they play important roles in, e.g., the fundamental interactions).

E_j energy first becomes operant at level j , and so it is *native* to that level. Thus, E_1 energy is native to level 1, E_2 energy is native to level 2, and so on. Note in particular that, since E_1 energy is native to level 1, then it is *independent* of \mathbf{d}_1 , \mathbf{d}_2 , \mathbf{d}_3 , level 2, level 3, etc.

4.3 A quantum of action

Recall that the dimension of time is associated with \mathbf{d}_1 . Since \mathbf{d}_1 does not exist at levels 0 and 1, then time also does not exist there; thus, all time intervals are zero at those levels. Indeed, we can say that levels 0 and 1 are *independent of time*. But \mathbf{d}_1 *does* exist at level 2 and above; so time exists there, and presumably all significant (i.e. nontrivial) time intervals at those levels are nonzero (and positive).

Thus, at level 1, energy is nonzero, but time is zero. At level 2 (and above), however, both energy and time (intervals) are *nonzero*. Consequently, at level 2 and above, the *product*

of energy and time – the quantity known as *action* – is nonzero, and thus has a positive lower bound; i.e., at level 2 (and above) the action is *quantized*. We thus have the derivation of an action *quantum*, which we interpret to be the basis for the empirically-known “quantum of action”, commonly referred to as *Planck’s constant* and denoted as h .

In the present model, therefore, the quantum of action, h , depends on both \mathbf{d}_0 and \mathbf{d}_1 , and so does not exist at levels 0 and 1, but only comes into being at level 2. Thus, quantum mechanics, which is based on h , also comes into being at level 2. And therefore, due to the scope rule, both h and quantum mechanics are operant at level 2 and above; i.e. they are *native* to level 2. Note that the advent of h at this relatively late stage (level 2) in the system is in contrast to the usual notion in which the quantum of action is assumed to (magically) operate at *all* phases in the construction of the physical universe.

The late advent of h has the following immediate consequences:

- Because h is not operant at levels 0 and 1, then the system is not quantum mechanical at those primal levels, and so it is not fundamentally quantum mechanical. Since this system is our model for constructing the physical universe, we conclude that the physical universe is not fundamentally quantum mechanical, and thus cannot have originated from a quantum effect (e.g. a “primordial quantum fluctuation”) – because the *source/origin* of the system is at level 0, and h does not exist there.
- The energy of quantum-vacuum fluctuations (or zero-point energy) necessarily depends on h , which (as we have found) is native to level 2. Since \mathbf{d}_0 energy exists only at level 1, then quantum-vacuum energy is clearly *not* \mathbf{d}_0 energy. This result will be shown (in section 4.4.1) to have an important consequence for the cosmological constant problem.

4.4 Energy distribution in space and time

In constructing the fundamental sequence ($\mathbf{d}_0, \mathbf{d}_1, \mathbf{d}_2, \mathbf{d}_3$), we know how the \mathbf{d}_k energies are distributed among the *levels* (i.e. \mathbf{d}_k energy is input into level $k + 1$), but how are they distributed in space and time? The following five factors of the model dominate the spatial and temporal distribution of these energies:

1. The displacements \mathbf{d}_0 and \mathbf{d}_1 are prior to, and thus *independent of*, ordinary space (sections 3.1 and 3.4).
2. At levels 0 and 1, neither time nor h exist.
3. At level 2 (and above), both time and h exist, and are thus in effect/operant.
4. By the nesting rule, the displacement \mathbf{d}_k is nested/contained/enveloped within the scope of the prior displacement \mathbf{d}_{k-1} ($k = 1, 2, 3$).
5. At level 3 (and above), the space S_{12}^3 is nested/confined within S_{02}^3 , which in turn is nested/confined within S_{01}^3 (ordinary space) (section 3.2).

The role of these factors in shaping energy distribution in space and time is elaborated in the next few subsections.

4.4.1 Aspects of \mathbf{d}_0 -energy distribution: dark energy

Recall that ordinary space is constructed when the displacement \mathbf{d}_0 is viewed from the perspective of \mathbf{d}_1 – and that \mathbf{d}_0 is prior to, and thus *independent of*, that space (factor 1). Note also that, given its priority to ordinary space, then (by the scope rule) \mathbf{d}_0 *is* operant (and does manifest) throughout that space.

Now suppose that \mathbf{d}_0 (or some aspect of the \mathbf{d}_0 process) operates or manifests *nonuniformly* within the ordinary space so constructed; e.g., it manifests with a particular position or direction, or as a vector or vector field. Then \mathbf{d}_0 would be operating/manifesting as a variable function of position or direction within that space, and thus be functionally *dependent* on ordinary space – thereby contradicting factor 1. We therefore conclude: The view of \mathbf{d}_0 from the perspective of \mathbf{d}_1 not only constructs a uniform ordinary space, but also has the result that \mathbf{d}_0 (or any aspect of the \mathbf{d}_0 process) must operate/manifest *uniformly* throughout that space.

This leads immediately to a further conclusion: \mathbf{d}_0 energy, which the \mathbf{d}_0 process inputs into level 1, must be distributed *uniformly* throughout the volume of ordinary space, and cannot manifest as a vector field. Consequently, it seems that \mathbf{d}_0 energy must manifest within ordinary space as a uniform *scalar* field (as already alluded to in section 3.4).

The absence of h at level 1 (factor 2) means that \mathbf{d}_0 energy (which is input into level 1) *cannot* be quantized or broken into chunks – and so it always constitutes a *single*, continuous entity. Thus, the distribution of \mathbf{d}_0 energy throughout ordinary space is always *perfectly* uniform and smooth, on both the large *and* small scales. In addition, since time does not exist at level 1, we assume (as per special relativity) that this single entity at level 1 is *massless*.

Recall again that the \mathbf{d}_0 process inputs \mathbf{d}_0 energy into *level 1*, but time is native to *level 2* (factor 3). Thus the \mathbf{d}_0 process is *prior* to time. By postulate 4, this means that the \mathbf{d}_0 process is *independent of time* – and is therefore a *continual* process, thereby producing a *stream* of \mathbf{d}_0 energy into level 1 that never stops, and so must be happening right now. Consequently, the *quantity* of \mathbf{d}_0 energy is *always* increasing.

As concluded above, the \mathbf{d}_0 process must distribute its \mathbf{d}_0 energy *uniformly* throughout ordinary space. Since this process is also independent of time, then it is *constant in time*. Thus, the continual stream of \mathbf{d}_0 energy into the system via the \mathbf{d}_0 process produces an influx of energy per unit volume of space that is uniform throughout space, and constant in time. In other words, the \mathbf{d}_0 process produces a *cosmological constant*.

Furthermore, since \mathbf{d}_0 (as seen by \mathbf{d}_1) *is* ordinary space, then it is clear that \mathbf{d}_0 energy is just the energy of space itself, and vice versa (as already alluded to in section 3.4). And, given that *dark energy* [10–12] is an input of energy into the system that constructs new *space*, then dark energy must be \mathbf{d}_0 energy.

Taken all together, the above results suggest the following identifications:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{dark energy} &= \mathbf{d}_0 \text{ energy} \\ &= \text{a cosmological constant.} \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

Thus, as we found above for \mathbf{d}_0 energy, dark energy is a *level-1* phenomenon; is prior to, and independent of, h and quantum mechanics; and is *not* quantizable. Conversely, energy forms that are native to *level 2* or above, such as the quantum-vacuum/zero-point energies (section 4.3), are *not* \mathbf{d}_0 energy, and so *cannot* contribute to dark energy or the cosmological constant. This result might be sufficient to eliminate the “cosmological constant problem” [12, 13].

4.4.2 Three epochs of \mathbf{d}_0 -energy distribution

The above result (4), equating \mathbf{d}_0 energy with a cosmological constant, was derived with our current perspective in mind. That is, it answers the question: How does the continual \mathbf{d}_0 -energy process manifest from the perspective of an observer within existing/established ordinary space? Answer: It manifests as a cosmological constant.

We may, however, distinguish *three* different phases or epochs of \mathbf{d}_0 -energy distribution, and ask how the \mathbf{d}_0 -energy process manifests in each of them.

The *third* epoch, or epoch 3, is the situation that we have just described (section 4.4.1), in which the \mathbf{d}_0 -energy process manifests as a cosmological constant, and includes the present era.

Epoch 1 is the situation that is prior to the existence of \mathbf{d}_1 and ordinary space, in which \mathbf{d}_0 energy is only distributed linearly along the length of \mathbf{d}_0 .

Epoch 2 is the situation that (as described in section 3.7) is triggered by the advent of \mathbf{d}_1 , in which ordinary space rapidly expands from a volume of zero to a volume of around $d_{0,0}^3$. The same reasoning that we used for epoch 3 (section 4.4.1) also applies in this situation, and allows us to conclude that: In epoch 2, which may also be called the inflationary epoch, the \mathbf{d}_0 energy manifests as a uniform scalar-energy field that drives the rapid expansion of space. That is, the \mathbf{d}_0 energy manifests in epoch 2 as a so-called “inflaton” field. [8]

In summary, this inflaton field, and the cosmological constant, are just two different phases of the \mathbf{d}_0 -energy distribution; i.e., they are different aspects of the *same* \mathbf{d}_0 process.

4.4.3 Aspects of \mathbf{d}_1 -energy distribution: the Higgs field and level-2 objects

Recall that factor 1 applies for \mathbf{d}_1 , just as it does for \mathbf{d}_0 ; i.e., \mathbf{d}_1 is prior to, and thus *independent of*, ordinary space. Hence, the results that we derived above for \mathbf{d}_0 using that factor are valid also for \mathbf{d}_1 . To wit: (a) \mathbf{d}_1 is operant/does manifest throughout ordinary space; (b) \mathbf{d}_1 operates/manifests *uniformly* throughout ordinary space; (c) \mathbf{d}_1 energy is distributed uniformly throughout ordinary space; and (d) \mathbf{d}_1 and \mathbf{d}_1 energy cannot manifest as vectors, or vector fields, within ordinary space.

Thus, *by factor 1*, the \mathbf{d}_1 process must distribute its \mathbf{d}_1 energy within ordinary space as a *uniform scalar field*. However, since \mathbf{d}_1 energy is input into *level 2*, where both h and time

are operant (factor 3), then (unlike \mathbf{d}_0 /dark energy at level 1) the \mathbf{d}_1 -scalar-energy field *is* quantizable, and can be time-dependent – which can produce small-scale deviations from the otherwise perfect uniformity (of \mathbf{d}_1 -energy distribution) that we would expect from the influence of factor 1 alone. Nevertheless, as indicated above, the overall distribution of \mathbf{d}_1 energy within ordinary space is dominated by factor 1, and so we expect it to be uniform on the large scale.

Since the construction of ordinary space depends on the \mathbf{d}_1 displacement, then it also depends on \mathbf{d}_1 energy (as well as \mathbf{d}_0 energy). The \mathbf{d}_1 energy that is involved in constructing ordinary space will be adjunctive to the \mathbf{d}_0 energy of that space, permanently manifesting as a uniform, but quantizable, scalar-energy field that is operant throughout ordinary space. We interpret that this permanent, uniform, \mathbf{d}_1 -scalar-energy field at level 2 – arising as a necessary adjunct in the process of constructing ordinary space – is just the *Higgs field*. [14] Since it is *not* \mathbf{d}_0 energy, then the \mathbf{d}_1 /Higgs field is thereby “cut off” from contributing to dark energy.

Now let us assume that some of the \mathbf{d}_1 -energy field at level 2 is *not* involved in constructing ordinary space, and so is not part of the Higgs field. This extra \mathbf{d}_1 energy at level 2 is thus *not* adjunctive to the \mathbf{d}_0 energy of ordinary space, and so we assume that its quantization can cause it to be broken up/partitioned into a *multiplicity* of smaller chunks, yielding what we will generically refer to as *level-2 objects*. Since *time* exists at level 2, we assume that these level-2 objects possess *mass* (as per special relativity), and also that their production can be time-dependent/time-limited, thereby yielding a *finite* number of them. Furthermore, these objects can acquire vector properties (e.g. spin, relative position, relative velocity) by processes to be described in section 5.

4.4.4 Basic distribution of \mathbf{d}_2 energy and \mathbf{d}_3 energy

Since ordinary space is native to level 2, but \mathbf{d}_2 is native to level 3, then the \mathbf{d}_2 displacement/process (which inputs \mathbf{d}_2 energy into level 3) is *subsequent to* ordinary space, and so (in contrast to \mathbf{d}_0 and \mathbf{d}_1) everything about it can be functionally dependent on that space. Thus: (a) even without help from h , \mathbf{d}_2 energy can be distributed *nonuniformly* within ordinary space; (b) there is nothing fundamental stopping \mathbf{d}_2 or \mathbf{d}_2 energy from manifesting as a vector, or vector field; and so, (c) in contrast to the \mathbf{d}_0 and \mathbf{d}_1 processes, the \mathbf{d}_2 process *does not* necessarily produce a uniform scalar-energy field. (And similarly for the \mathbf{d}_3 process, which inputs \mathbf{d}_3 energy into level 4.) Apparently, then, the present model yields *exactly two* fundamental, permanent, uniform scalar-energy fields: the one attributed to \mathbf{d}_0 energy (which currently manifests as a cosmological constant/dark energy), and the one attributed to \mathbf{d}_1 energy (which manifests as the Higgs field).

Moreover, since \mathbf{d}_2 is not involved in the construction of ordinary space, then (in contrast to \mathbf{d}_1 energy at level 2) no \mathbf{d}_2 energy is adjunctive to the \mathbf{d}_0 energy of that space. This result, coupled with the fact that h is operant for the \mathbf{d}_2 process, means it is likely that *all* of the \mathbf{d}_2 energy input into level 3 can be broken up into a multiplicity of smaller chunks, yielding what we will generically refer to as *level-3 objects*. Since *time* exists at level 3, we assume that

these level-3 objects possess *mass* (as per special relativity), and also that their production can be time-dependent/time-limited, thereby yielding a *finite* number of them. As with the level-2 objects, the level-3 objects can then acquire the properties of spin, relative position, and relative velocity by processes to be described in section 5. (And similarly for \mathbf{d}_3 energy at level 4, with corresponding “level-4 objects”.)

Given that all of the \mathbf{d}_2 energy may be partitioned/broken up, then its small-scale distribution within ordinary space is likely granular or chunky, and thus *nonuniform*. To determine its *large-scale* distribution, however, let us recall its provenance (section 4.2): it originates from \mathbf{d}_1 energy at level 2, which is then displaced up to level 3 as \mathbf{d}_2 energy. Consequently, since the former (\mathbf{d}_1 energy at level 2) is distributed uniformly on the large scale, then the latter (\mathbf{d}_2 energy at level 3) will also be distributed uniformly on the large scale. In other words, the \mathbf{d}_2 -energy distribution “follows the lead” of the \mathbf{d}_1 -energy distribution, and is thus uniform on the large scale. (And similarly for \mathbf{d}_3 energy at level 4, if any: it originates from \mathbf{d}_2 energy at level 3 that is distributed uniformly on the large scale, and so it also is distributed uniformly on the large scale throughout ordinary space.)

4.4.5 A smooth primordial volume of ordinary space

Let us assume that the sequence ($\mathbf{d}_0, \mathbf{d}_1, \mathbf{d}_2, \mathbf{d}_3$) of fundamental displacements is in place within the first instants of time, with the universe at that stage having a volume of V_{fs} (the volume of the universe once the *fundamental sequence* is in place). Relating this to the volume of the universe at the end of inflation (section 3.7), we have $V_{fs} \geq d_{0,0}^3$.

From our results above, we can say that:

- The distribution of \mathbf{d}_0 energy throughout ordinary space (as either an inflaton field, or as dark energy) is perfectly uniform on both the large and small scales (section 4.4.1).
- The distribution of \mathbf{d}_1 energy throughout ordinary space is uniform on the large scale, with some nonuniformities on the small scale (section 4.4.3).
- While their small-scale distributions are generally nonuniform, the \mathbf{d}_2 and \mathbf{d}_3 processes nevertheless “follow the lead” of the \mathbf{d}_1 -energy process and thus also distribute their energies uniformly throughout ordinary space on the large scale (Section 4.4.4).

We therefore conclude that the overall distribution of energy throughout the primordial volume, V_{fs} , of ordinary space should be uniform and smooth on the large scale, with some nonuniformities on the small scale. Such a primordial distribution might then explain the large-scale uniformity of the cosmic microwave background (CMB), and also its small-scale nonuniformities. [15]

Note that, although the present model does include an inflation event, the smooth distribution of energy throughout the primordial volume of space (and thus also in the CMB) might not depend on it. Rather, that smooth distribution is mainly (if not completely) a symmetry property that is rooted in fundamental independence relations: the independence of \mathbf{d}_0 and \mathbf{d}_1 from ordinary space (i.e., factor 1).

In addition, we note that the volume V_{fs} comprises *all* of the ordinary space that is extant once the fundamental sequence is in place, not just a portion that comes from an earlier “patch” of space. The present model thus seems to produce a *single* universe, not a runaway multiverse.

4.4.6 The standard viewpoint/perspective

In the process of \mathbf{d}_1 viewing \mathbf{d}_0 , the former is the *observing* entity (i.e. the *observer*), and the latter is the *observed* entity. We already know how the observed entity (\mathbf{d}_0) manifests in this process: as a three-dimensional space (i.e., ordinary space). It is appropriate to also ask how the observing entity (\mathbf{d}_1) manifests as a result of this process.

By factor 4, \mathbf{d}_1 is nested within the scope of \mathbf{d}_0 . So, when \mathbf{d}_0 (as seen by \mathbf{d}_1) becomes *three-dimensional* ordinary space, \mathbf{d}_1 will see itself as nested/contained/embedded *within* that space. Thus, a consequence of \mathbf{d}_1 viewing \mathbf{d}_0 is that the former (\mathbf{d}_1) manifests as a kind of viewpoint or perspective within the three-dimensional ordinary space that is generated by the process.

Since \mathbf{d}_0 and \mathbf{d}_1 are jointly operant at level 2 and above, then this viewpoint for \mathbf{d}_1 is native to level 2; i.e., all objects at level 2 and above will have this *same* basic viewpoint or perspective, and thus see themselves as nested/embedded within ordinary space. We may therefore refer to this common viewpoint as the *standard viewpoint* or *standard perspective*; and we reiterate that it is native to level 2.

Suppose now that the standard viewpoint/perspective establishes or constitutes a particular position or orientation for \mathbf{d}_1 within ordinary space. Then \mathbf{d}_1 would be functionally dependent on ordinary space, thereby contradicting factor 1. We thus conclude that the standard perspective does not have particular position or direction properties (in ordinary space) associated with it; and so it merely constitutes a kind of *generic vista* that manifests for all objects at level 2 and above.

4.4.7 Further aspects of \mathbf{d}_2 -energy distribution (at level 3): confined substructure

In section 3.2 we found that – in addition to ordinary space and time – four extra spaces, comprising eight extra dimensions, come into existence at level 3; these extra spaces are denoted [e.g. in (2)] as S_{20}^1 , S_{21}^1 , S_{02}^3 , and S_{12}^3 . We now ask: From the perspective of a level-3 object, *where* are these extra spaces located?

We concluded in the preceding section that the basic perspective of a level-3 object is the *standard* perspective; i.e., a level-3 object sees itself as being nested/embedded within three-dimensional ordinary space. Since the standard perspective is native to level 2, then it is prior to, independent of, and *outside the scope of* the extra spaces that come into existence at level 3. This means that those extra spaces cannot be operant or manifest within the space that the level-3 object sees itself embedded in (i.e., they can’t encroach on the standard perspective); for, if they were to manifest there, then they would be violating the independence of that space, and operating outside of their legitimate scopes.

Hence, it seems we must conclude that the extra spaces of a level-3 object are *internal to* – i.e. confined and compacted *within* – the level-3 object. A level-3 object thus partitions its world into *two* zones: an *outside* or exterior zone, which it sees itself nested/embedded in; and an *inside* zone, which corresponds to the restricted scopes of its extra spaces, and forms the *interior* of the level-3 object. In short, a level-3 object has *confined internal spaces*, which opens the possibility for confined internal *structure*.

The extra spaces at level 3 – S_{20}^1 , S_{21}^1 , S_{02}^3 , and S_{12}^3 – thereby comprise an internal microworld of a level-3 object. We will assume that the construction of this microworld basically recapitulates the macroworld construction that is native to level 2, as already described. That is, we assume that the spaces S_{20}^1 and S_{21}^1 operate as extra one-dimensional parameters in this internal microworld, similar to the way ordinary time (S_{10}^1) operates; and that S_{02}^3 and S_{12}^3 form three-dimensional spaces of this internal microworld, where the latter space is nested/confined within the former (factor 5). The following argument brings us to a reasonable interpretation of the level-3 objects.

Since S_{02}^3 is a mode of the displacement \mathbf{d}_0 , which is independent of h , then we will assume that it (S_{02}^3) manifests as a *single, continuous*, three-dimensional space (i.e. having no discontinuities or chunkiness). On the other hand, since S_{12}^3 is a mode of the displacement \mathbf{d}_1 , which is native to level 2 (where h is operant), then let us suppose that its continuity may be broken. In particular, suppose that S_{12}^3 is broken into *three, discrete*, one-dimensional spaces – i.e. three discrete degrees of freedom.

It would then be reasonable to assume that at least some of the \mathbf{d}_2 and E_3 energies of a level-3 object will be distributed into *each* of these three, discrete degrees of freedom for S_{12}^3 – resulting in a *triplet* of energy nodes or particles *within* the level-3 object. Consequently, each level-3 object would have internal structure that includes a triplet of subparticles that are *confined* within the object. This suggests that we interpret level-3 objects to be the particles known as *baryons*, and their three subparticles to be the objects known as *quarks*. In this way, the present model may account for the existence of baryonic quarks, and also their confinement within the baryons.

Furthermore, recall that “ E_3 energy” is a new identity/property that energy acquires when it is placed into level 3 (section 4.2). Likewise, when E_3 energy is placed into each of the three, discrete, internal degrees of freedom (of S_{12}^3) for a level-3 object, let us suppose that it acquires *additional* identities/properties as a result, thereby constituting three *subtypes* of E_3 energy. Of course, in this context the well-established notion of “color charge” comes to mind. Let us suppose therefore that the three subtypes of E_3 energy should be designated as E_{3r} , E_{3g} , and E_{3b} ; where r , g , and b stand for red, green, and blue.

So, under the above scheme, color charges are just different subtypes of E_3 energy. And we note that such a result comports with the following notion of a minimalist physics: that everything about the universe (including so-called “charges”) can be reduced to a simple ontology consisting of just energy, together with its different arrangements, relations, and behaviors.³ To wit, “color charge” is just a shorthand term for the way that energy behaves

³In the present model, however, the arrangements, relations, and behaviors of energy depend themselves on the fundamental *levels* and *displacements*, as well as postulate 4. Thus, at bottom, the proper minimalist

when it is “arranged” into the discrete internal degrees of freedom described above.

4.4.8 Substructure at level 4

Since everything at level 3 is inherited by level 4, then level-4 objects would (like level-3 objects) see themselves as being nested/embedded within ordinary space, and also have a substructure of three discrete particles or quarks. However, in section 3.2 it was determined that level 4 generates three new, three-dimensional spaces, denoted as S_{x3}^3 ($x = 0, 1, 2$). These spaces will be internal to (and compacted within) S_{02}^3 and S_{12}^3 . It seems likely, therefore, that the three subparticles/quarks within level-4 objects would *themselves* contain internal structure (whereas the quarks at level 3 likely have no internal structure).

4.4.9 The extra single dimensions that are native to level 3

The extra single dimensions S_{20}^1 and S_{21}^1 that are native to level 3 are subsequent to ordinary space S_{01}^3 , but likely prior to S_{02}^3 and S_{12}^3 . Objects at level 3 (and above) will therefore see those single dimensions as *internal* and compacted within ordinary space (as already concluded in section 4.4.7); whereas S_{02}^3 and S_{12}^3 will see them as being operant everywhere within their three-dimensional spaces (just as ordinary time is operant everywhere within ordinary space – section 3.5). Thus, as alluded to in section 4.4.7, S_{20}^1 and S_{21}^1 might produce something akin to extra “time” dimensions that would apply to the internal three-dimensional spaces of objects at level 3 and above (e.g. baryons).

4.5 The spectrum of entities and object types constructed by the model (so far)

We have identified the scalar field at level 1 as dark energy, the scalar field at level 2 as the Higgs field, and the objects at level 3 as the baryons. What about the objects at level 2?

We first note that there are no internal spaces at level 2 (in contrast to levels 3 and 4), so level-2 objects have no internal structure; i.e. they are *structureless*. Second, as concluded in section 4.4.3, the level-2 objects have *mass*. We therefore identify the objects at level 2 as the *leptons*.

These identifications are illustrated in Fig. 2.

Now recall our finding above that level-2 and level-3 objects have the standard viewpoint/perspective, and thus see themselves as nested/embedded within ordinary space. Since we humans are composed of level-2 and level-3 objects (i.e. electrons, protons and neutrons), then it makes sense that we too have the standard perspective, and thus see ourselves as being nested within ordinary space. Moreover, we *do not* see the extra spaces at level 3 and above manifesting at large within the ordinary space of our experience; which also makes sense, since those extra spaces form the interiors of, and are confined within, objects at level 3 and above (e.g. protons and neutrons).

ontology for physics might be: energy, levels, displacements, and the relations between them (postulate 4).

Fig. 2: The spectrum of entities and object/particle types that the model has constructed so far: Dark energy at level 1, the Higgs field and leptons at level 2, and baryons at level 3.

4.6 Associating displacements and energy types with entity/particle properties

A basic difference between a (hypothetical) level-0 entity and dark energy is that the latter gravitates, and thus has a property that we might call “gravitational charge”, whereas the former presumably does not gravitate, and thus lacks that property. In the present model, the basic difference between an entity at level 0 and dark energy (at level 1) is that the latter has the displacement \mathbf{d}_0 and corresponding energy E_1 , whereas the former does not. Thus, \mathbf{d}_0 and E_1 energy are associated with (and, indeed, appear to be *necessary* for producing) gravitational charge (i.e., the ability to gravitate).

Likewise, a basic difference between dark energy and leptons is that the latter have the properties known as *lepton number* (or *lepton charge*), mass, and possibly electric charge; whereas the former presumably has none of those properties. In the present model, the basic difference between dark energy (at level 1) and leptons (at level 2) is that the latter have the displacement \mathbf{d}_1 and corresponding energy E_2 , whereas the former does not. Thus, \mathbf{d}_1 and E_2 energy are associated with (and, indeed, appear to be *necessary* for producing) lepton charge, electric charge, and mass.

Finally, a basic difference between leptons and baryons is that the latter have the properties known as *baryon number* (or *baryon charge*) and color charge, and the former do not. In the present model, the basic difference between leptons (at level 2) and baryons (at level 3) is that the latter have the displacement \mathbf{d}_2 and corresponding energy E_3 , whereas the former do not. Thus, \mathbf{d}_2 and E_3 energy are associated with (and, indeed, appear to be *necessary* for producing) baryon charge and color charge.

4.7 Analogy with biological genetics

In constructing the sequence $(\mathbf{d}_0, \mathbf{d}_1, \mathbf{d}_2, \mathbf{d}_3)$, we might consider (by analogy with biological genetics) the set of displacements that are operant at a given level to be the “genome” for an entity/particle class (or “genus”) at that level. Thus, the genome for an entity at level 0 is $\{ \}$; the genome for dark energy at level 1 is $\{\mathbf{d}_0\}$; the genome for the Higgs field and leptons

at level 2 is $\{\mathbf{d}_0, \mathbf{d}_1\}$; the genome for baryons at level 3 is $\{\mathbf{d}_0, \mathbf{d}_1, \mathbf{d}_2\}$; and the genome for level-4 objects is $\{\mathbf{d}_0, \mathbf{d}_1, \mathbf{d}_2, \mathbf{d}_3\}$.

In addition, we might think of the individual displacements $\mathbf{d}_0, \mathbf{d}_1, \mathbf{d}_2$, etc., within the genomes as “genes” for properties or attributes; e.g., \mathbf{d}_0 is the gene for gravitational charge and E_1 energy; \mathbf{d}_1 is the gene for lepton charge, electric charge, mass, and E_2 energy; and \mathbf{d}_2 is the gene for baryon charge, color charge, and E_3 energy. Moreover, epigenetic analogies may also apply. For example, we may think of the lepton-number attribute of \mathbf{d}_1 as being “turned on” at level 2, allowing its expression there, but “turned off” at level 3, suppressing its expression.

The genomes and resulting entity/particle classes at each successive level constitute “generations” of entities. Thus, dark energy at level 1 is the first-generation entity; the Higgs field and leptons at level 2 are entities of the second generation; baryons at level 3 are entities of the third generation; and objects at level 4 (if any) are entities of the fourth generation. Each such generation inherits the genes (indeed, the complete genome) of the prior generation.

We may also think of the energy types – E_1, E_2, E_3 , and E_4 – as having genomes, which correspond to the displacements that are operant at their *native* levels. Thus E_1 has the genome $\{\mathbf{d}_0\}$; E_2 has the genome $\{\mathbf{d}_0, \mathbf{d}_1\}$; E_3 has the genome $\{\mathbf{d}_0, \mathbf{d}_1, \mathbf{d}_2\}$; and E_4 has the genome $\{\mathbf{d}_0, \mathbf{d}_1, \mathbf{d}_2, \mathbf{d}_3\}$. Or, more compactly, E_j has the genome $\{\mathbf{d}_0, \mathbf{d}_1, \dots, \mathbf{d}_{j-1}\}$, for $j = 1, 2, 3, 4$.

4.8 The default position of a particle

From the model developed so far, what can we say about the *position* of an object/particle? Consider, for example, a level-3 object (e.g. a proton) with genome $\{\mathbf{d}_0, \mathbf{d}_1, \mathbf{d}_2\}$. What can we say about the position of such an object?

To say that an object/particle has a certain position is to say that its attributes/properties are located at that position. We found above (section 4.6) that different particle properties are associated with (and dependent on) different displacement components in their genomes; e.g., electric charge and mass are associated with \mathbf{d}_1 , and baryon charge is associated with \mathbf{d}_2 .

By factor 4 (section 4.4), \mathbf{d}_2 (and the properties associated with it) are contained/enveloped within \mathbf{d}_1 ; likewise, \mathbf{d}_1 (and the properties associated with it) are contained within \mathbf{d}_0 . Hence, *all* of a particle’s properties are contained/enveloped within its \mathbf{d}_0 component. Therefore, the question “where in ordinary space is a particle located?” can be simplified to “where is the particle’s \mathbf{d}_0 component located?” In other words, the sharpness of a particle’s location in ordinary space is only as sharp as the location of its \mathbf{d}_0 component.

Now, if a particle’s \mathbf{d}_0 component were to have a particular position within ordinary space, then it would be manifesting *nonuniformly*, and thus be functionally dependent on that space – thereby contradicting factor 1 (section 4.4). Hence, the particle’s \mathbf{d}_0 component must manifest *uniformly* throughout ordinary space; and so (since a particle’s location follows the location of its \mathbf{d}_0 component) the particle itself must manifest uniformly throughout that space. In other words, the position of the particle is *everywhere* in space; indeed, it is *uniformly smeared out across ordinary space*. Alternatively, we may simply say that the particle manifests as a

uniform *field*, filling all of space (thereby comporting with the conception of a “free” particle in quantum theory).

Although such “smearing out” across space of a particle’s location is a well-established aspect of quantum mechanics, it has nevertheless been a continuing enigma. However, it now has the following simple explanation within the present model: A particle’s \mathbf{d}_0 component is independent of ordinary space, and so the particle must manifest uniformly throughout that space. That is, the uniform smearing across space of a particle’s position is a *symmetry* property that originates in a fundamental independence relation that is an instance of postulate 4. It is the *same* independence relation that is responsible for the uniformity (isotropy and homogeneity) of ordinary space itself, and also for the uniform distribution of dark energy throughout that space.

We know, however, that particles can also go on to acquire, e.g., definite positions within ordinary space. (In section 5 we will describe some of the processes by which this can occur in the present model.) Thus, the uniformly-smear-out position of a particle may be qualified as its *default* position. Likewise, the manifestation of a particle as a uniform field may be qualified as its default *state*.

4.9 Fundamental interactions

The displacements that we have discussed so far may be described as *forward* displacements, since (as described in postulate 1) they go from a prior level to a subsequent level (i.e. they are directed *away* from level 0). We associated these displacements with the input of energy into higher/subsequent levels.

We now want to introduce the concept of *reverse* or *backward* displacement, which goes in the opposite direction: from a subsequent level to a prior level (i.e. *toward* level 0). Specifically, I propose that each forward displacement $\mathbf{d}_0, \mathbf{d}_1, \mathbf{d}_2, \mathbf{d}_3$, has a corresponding backward displacement, which we denote as $-\mathbf{d}_0, -\mathbf{d}_1, -\mathbf{d}_2, -\mathbf{d}_3$, respectively.

Basically, for an object/entity that has E_{k+1} energy, we define $-\mathbf{d}_k$ as “the backward displacement of E_{k+1} energy onto level k ” ($k = 0, 1, 2, 3$). That is, such a backward displacement, $-\mathbf{d}_k$, takes E_{k+1} energy (whose native level is $k + 1$) and places it at level k , yielding an entity/object/particle at that level. So, for example, a level-2 object (such as an electron) with E_2 energy may utilize the backward displacement $-\mathbf{d}_1$ to place E_2 energy onto level 1, yielding an object at that level. More generally, a *sequence* of n backward displacements, denoted as $(-\mathbf{d}_k, -\mathbf{d}_{k-1}, \dots, -\mathbf{d}_{k-n+1})$, can take E_{k+1} energy and place it at level $k - n + 1$, yielding an entity/object/particle at that level (where $n \leq k + 1$).

Backward displacement in the present model is in some ways similar to *projection* in ordinary geometry. Consider a three-dimensional sphere for example: it becomes a *two*-dimensional circle when projected onto the x-y plane; and the circle becomes a *one*-dimensional line when projected onto the x-axis. So, with each “backward” projection the space dimensions of the object are reduced by one. Similar things happen with backward *displacement* in the present model (as described below).

In addition to forward and backward displacements, let us also define a *lateral* or *intralevel*

displacement of E_j energy, which places that energy onto E_j 's *native* level (i.e. level j), thereby yielding an object/particle at that level. Backward and lateral/intralevel displacements may be classified together as *nonforward* displacements.⁴

The basic theme below is that *all* fundamental interactions are due to nonforward displacements of E_j energy – either lateral/intralevel displacement onto its native level, j ; or backward displacement onto a prior level.

4.9.1 The electromagnetic interaction

Recall that E_2 energy is native to level 2, and thus objects created by the fundamental sequence at level 2 or above (e.g. leptons and baryons) will possess it. We now ask, what happens when E_2 energy is backward displaced onto level 1 (via the operation that we have denoted as $-\mathbf{d}_1$)?

Since E_2 energy has the genome $\{\mathbf{d}_0, \mathbf{d}_1\}$, and loses its \mathbf{d}_1 component in the backward displacement ($-\mathbf{d}_1$), we could denote the genome for the resulting level-1 object as $\{\mathbf{d}_0\}$. But that would confuse it with the genome for dark energy, and also obscure the energy's *history* – of, inter alia, being the product of a *backward* displacement. A better way to denote its genome is therefore $\{\mathbf{d}_0, -\mathbf{d}_1\mathbf{d}_1\}$. This object has energy, but no electric charge (due to the net absence of \mathbf{d}_1 in its genome), and (due to the absence of \mathbf{d}_1 /time) is massless. Its “source”, if you will, is E_2 energy, which we have associated with electric charge. We interpret, therefore, that the object denoted by the genome $\{\mathbf{d}_0, -\mathbf{d}_1\mathbf{d}_1\}$, resulting from backward displacement of E_2 energy onto level 1, is the *photon*. Consequently, we say that *the photon is a level-1 object that is produced by backward displacement* (in contrast to dark energy, which is a level-1 entity produced by *forward* displacement). Furthermore, we interpret that the backward displacement of E_2 energy onto level 1 (via $-\mathbf{d}_1$) is just the *electromagnetic interaction* (actually, it is the *emission* phase of that interaction; the absorption phase will be discussed later). In general, then, it is suggested that backward displacement is responsible for at least some of the fundamental interactions.

At level 2 the dimensionality of \mathbf{d}_0 (with respect to \mathbf{d}_1) is 3, and the dimensionality of \mathbf{d}_1 (with respect to \mathbf{d}_0) is 1 (i.e. the dimensions of ordinary space and time, respectively). When E_2 energy is backward displaced onto level 1 (via the operation $-\mathbf{d}_1$), the dimension of time (associated with \mathbf{d}_1) vanishes to zero. Likewise, the component of \mathbf{d}_0 parallel to \mathbf{d}_1 also vanishes, leaving only *two* space dimensions (which may thus be called the *residual* dimensions, or the *residual 2-space*, of \mathbf{d}_0 with respect to \mathbf{d}_1), both of which are orthogonal to \mathbf{d}_1 . In other words, the backward displacement of E_2 energy onto level 1 produces an object for which the time dimension does not exist, and whose space dimensions are reduced from three to two – which agrees with the results implied by special relativity for the photon, further supporting our interpretation that photons are the result of backward displacement of E_2 energy onto level 1.

Light (i.e. electromagnetic radiation) is thus energy that starts out at level 2 (or above) and is backward displaced onto level 1 (where time does not exist). Its origin at level 2 or

⁴These new types of displacement will later be incorporated into a *fifth* postulate.

above (where time *does* exist) endows this energy with a *history*, an aspect of which is its exposure to h , which (I propose) endows light energy with its quantum properties. Dark energy, in contrast, is a *strictly* level-1 entity/phenomenon; so we can say that *it is energy without a history*. Its lack of a history at level 2 or above means that dark energy has never been exposed to h , and so it is not quantized, and has no quantum properties (e.g., as determined earlier, it has no quantum chunkiness).

It seems, then, that the quantum properties and two-dimensional space of light/photons may all be residual aspects (or, if you will, *residues*) that stem from the energy's history at level 2 or above.

4.9.2 The strong interaction

Recall that E_3 energy is native to level 3, and thus objects created by the fundamental sequence at level 3 or above (e.g. baryons) will possess it. We now ask, what happens when E_3 energy – with genome $\{\mathbf{d}_0, \mathbf{d}_1, \mathbf{d}_2\}$, and which we have associated with color charge (sections 4.4.7 and 4.6) – is backward displaced onto level 2 (via the operation that we have denoted as $-\mathbf{d}_2$)?

As stated earlier, when \mathbf{d}_1 is related to \mathbf{d}_2 the dimensionality of the former is 3 (i.e. S_{12}^3), and the dimensionality of the latter is 1 (i.e. S_{21}^1). When E_3 energy is backward displaced onto level 2, the one dimension associated with \mathbf{d}_2 vanishes to zero, and the three dimensions associated with \mathbf{d}_1 are reduced to *two*. Recalling our earlier interpretation (section 4.4.7) that – at level 3 or above – the three, discrete, one-dimensional spaces associated with \mathbf{d}_1 (from the viewpoint of \mathbf{d}_2) are responsible for the *triple*-quark substructure of baryons, I now propose that the reduction of these dimensions down to two – when E_3 energy is backward displaced onto level 2 – is responsible for the production of objects with a *double*-quark substructure. Consequently, we interpret that the objects produced by backward displacement of E_3 energy onto level 2 are the *mesons* (which, indeed, are thought to have a double-quark – actually, quark-antiquark – substructure). So, in this sense, *the mesons are level-2 objects* whose genome may be denoted as $\{\mathbf{d}_0, \mathbf{d}_1, -\mathbf{d}_2\mathbf{d}_2\}$ – which comports with the mesons possessing energy, electric charge, mass, and zero net baryon charge.

We can therefore think of mesons as level-2 objects that contain *level-3-type* substructure (i.e. the two quarks). Such an outcome seems to be allowed by the nesting rule, since the (ontologically) subsequent level-3-type substructure is nested/contained/embedded within the (ontologically) prior level-2-type structure.

In the above description (of backward displacement of E_3 energy onto level 2), we utilized the residual 2-space of \mathbf{d}_1 with respect to \mathbf{d}_2 (to account for the double-quark substructure of mesons), but we neglected to mention another such space that arises in this process: the residual 2-space of \mathbf{d}_0 with respect to \mathbf{d}_2 ; i.e. the 2-space that remains when, due to backward displacement of E_3 energy onto level 2, the component of \mathbf{d}_0 in the direction of \mathbf{d}_2 vanishes. We have thus identified *three* residual 2-spaces: the residual 2-space of \mathbf{d}_0 with respect to \mathbf{d}_1 (introduced in section 4.9.1), which may be referred to as the *first* residual 2-space; the residual 2-space of \mathbf{d}_0 with respect to \mathbf{d}_2 , which may be referred to as the *second* residual

2-space; and the residual 2-space of \mathbf{d}_1 with respect to \mathbf{d}_2 , which may be referred to as the *third* residual 2-space. The numbering/ranking of these residual spaces reflects their order of priority. Given such priority relations, together with the nesting rule, we conclude that, where applicable: the third residual 2-space is nested/encapsulated/confined within the second, and the second is nested/confined within the first.

When E_3 energy is backward displaced onto level 2, only the second and third residual 2-spaces are applicable (since \mathbf{d}_1 is *still* operant at level 2, and thus the space of \mathbf{d}_0 with respect to \mathbf{d}_1 – i.e. *ordinary* space – is fully three dimensional). By the priority relations established above, the third residual 2-space, which yields the double-quark substructure of mesons, would be *confined* within the second – a result which might help to explain the confinement of quarks within mesons.

Consider now a process in which E_3 energy is backward displaced onto *level 1*, via the operations $-\mathbf{d}_2$ and $-\mathbf{d}_1$ – a *sequence* of backward displacements which may be denoted by $(-\mathbf{d}_2, -\mathbf{d}_1)$. The result of this process is an object at level 1 with genome $\{\mathbf{d}_0, -\mathbf{d}_1\mathbf{d}_1, -\mathbf{d}_2\mathbf{d}_2\}$, which (due to the absence of \mathbf{d}_1 and \mathbf{d}_2) is thus massless and possesses zero electric, lepton, and baryon charges. I propose that this object is the *gluon*.⁵

In this gluon-production process, the third residual 2-space would cease to exist (since \mathbf{d}_1 is not operant at level 1). So, whatever is left over from the backward-displacement sequence (double color charge?) would be confined within the *second* residual 2-space, which would be confined within the first. This result might help to explain the confinement of gluons and their color charges.

In summary, we interpret that the strong interaction as mediated by mesons is the result of backward displacement of E_3 energy onto level 2; and the strong interaction as mediated by gluons is the result of a sequence of backward displacements, $(-\mathbf{d}_2, -\mathbf{d}_1)$, of E_3 energy onto level 1.

4.9.3 The weak interaction, and electroweak unification

The weak interaction is known to be mediated by the W and Z bosons. Given that the W and Z possess mass, have zero baryon number, and have no internal structure (as far as we know), it follows that they are *level-2* objects in the present model. Thus the weak interaction involves the displacement of energy onto *level 2*, which thereby yields objects/particles at that level (i.e. the W and Z). We know that leptons participate in the weak interaction, and that (according to the present model) they are level-2 objects that possess E_1 energy and E_2 energy. So we must attribute the weak interaction to a nonforward displacement of either E_1 energy or E_2 energy. However, we can immediately rule out E_1 energy – with genome $\{\mathbf{d}_0\}$ – as a source of the weak interaction, since its intralevel and backward displacements would yield objects at levels 1 and 0, respectively (i.e. *not* at level 2, where the W and Z reside). And since *backward* displacement of E_2 energy would also yield an object at the

⁵Note that, due to the scope rule, level 1 is operant within the internal spaces of a level-3 object. Thus the backward displacement of E_3 energy onto level 1 (producing a gluon) can take place completely *within* the interior of a level-3 object (e.g. a proton).

wrong level (i.e. *level 1*), then it seems that we must attribute the weak interaction to an *intralevel*/lateral displacement of E_2 energy (onto level 2).

Since the *electromagnetic* interaction has *also* been attributed to a nonforward displacement of E_2 energy, then we can say that the electromagnetic and weak interactions have the *same* source – E_2 energy. As such, the present model might augment our understanding of “electroweak unification”; i.e., the electromagnetic and weak interactions are related or “unified” because (a) they both have the same source (E_2 energy), and (b) they both stem from the nonforward displacement of E_2 energy – where the former interaction is attributed to *backward* displacement of such energy (onto level 1), and the latter interaction is attributed to *lateral* displacement of that energy (*within* level 2). In addition, the lateralness (thus, possibly, *handedness*) of an *intralevel* displacement might be a clue to explaining why the weak interaction violates left-right symmetry, or parity.

Although it might be useful at some future time to develop a special notation to indicate in their genomes that the W and Z particles are products of *intralevel* displacement of E_2 energy, for now we will just denote them as having the same genome as level-2 objects that are produced by *forward* displacement – i.e. $\{\mathbf{d}_0, \mathbf{d}_1\}$.

4.9.4 The gravitational interaction

It is convenient to distinguish between two phenomenological types of gravity: the “attractive” type and the “repulsive” type; or, in short, “gravity-A” and “gravity-R”. When we mean both types, or we don’t need to distinguish between the two, or the context makes it clear which one we mean, then we may simply say “gravity”, or “the gravitational interaction”, etc.

In section 4.4.1, we found that gravity-R, or dark energy, is produced *exclusively* by the \mathbf{d}_0 process – i.e., by the continual input of \mathbf{d}_0 energy into level 1 of the system. Thus, in this sense, the *source* of gravity-R is the \mathbf{d}_0 process, or \mathbf{d}_0 energy. We now need to identify the (likely) source of gravity-A.

Following the pattern of the other interactions described above, we should attribute gravity-A to a *nonforward* displacement of one of the E_j energies ($j = 1, 2, 3, 4$). Previous results, however, allow us to narrow this down very quickly: Since dark energy is a source of gravity, and is a *level-1* phenomenon, then presumably the E_j -energy type to which we attribute gravity-A should also be present/available/operant at level 1 – a condition that *only* E_1 energy satisfies.

So it follows that we should attribute gravity-A to a nonforward displacement of E_1 energy – either backward displacement onto level 0, *or* lateral/intralevel displacement onto level 1. But which one? For reasons to be provided in section 6, we choose the latter; that is, we attribute gravity-A to the *lateral/intralevel* displacement of E_1 energy onto level 1 – which thereby identifies E_1 energy as the *source* of gravity-A. This means that the “graviton” (in common with the photon and the gluon) is a *level-1* object that is produced by nonforward displacement. Thus, the strong, electromagnetic, and gravitational interactions all utilize nonforward displacement of energy onto level 1.

Now, since \mathbf{d}_0 energy is *also* E_1 energy (but not always the converse; section 4.2), then we

can simply identify E_1 energy as the general source for *all* gravity, i.e. as the *gravitational charge*. Thus, in its form as \mathbf{d}_0 energy at level 1, E_1 energy is the source of gravity-R (dark energy); and, at level 1 or above, E_1 energy is also the source of gravity-A.

Our model for gravity therefore yields the following results and explanations concerning that interaction.

- **Nonquantization** (or, why gravity seems to defy attempts at quantization): Since the general source of gravity is E_1 energy (which is native to level 1), and since the quantum of action h is native to level 2, then the basis for the gravitational interaction is *prior* to, and thus independent of, h ; and so gravity is not fundamentally quantum mechanical.⁶ Or, in more figurative language, we might say: The basic ingredient for gravity (E_1 energy) is “up and running” at level 1, before quantum mechanics (i.e. h) “gets its boots on” at level 2.

So, as far as we can tell from the present model, gravity is *completely* independent of h and quantum mechanics – perhaps eliminating the need for a quantum theory of gravity.⁷

- **Universality**: Recall from section 4.2 that, in constructing the fundamental sequence ($\mathbf{d}_0, \mathbf{d}_1, \mathbf{d}_2, \mathbf{d}_3$), *all* of the energy that is involved – in whatever forms it might take (e.g., \mathbf{d}_0 energy, \mathbf{d}_1 energy, E_1 energy, E_2 energy, etc.) – shares the provenance of entering the system via the \mathbf{d}_0 process, and is therefore “ E_1 energy”. Consequently, the “intralevel/lateral displacement of E_1 energy within level 1” is a *universal* characteristic of all these energy forms and their associated entities/objects/particles (e.g. dark energy, leptons, baryons, etc). In other words, *all* of the energy associated with these things will laterally displace onto level 1, thereby making them sources of gravity-A. This would seem to account for the “universal” nature of the gravitational interaction.

4.9.5 Other possible fundamental interactions

Given our unified characterization of the fundamental interactions (excepting gravity-R) as resulting from “nonforward displacements of the E_j energies”, then the case for which $j = 4$ presents the possibility for new interaction types, via (a) backward displacement of E_4 energy, and (b) lateral/intralevel displacement of E_4 energy (onto level 4). Likewise, for $j = 3$, there might be an interaction type that is due to lateral displacement of E_3 energy (onto level 3). However, due to the confinement that occurs for everything at level 3 and above (including for E_3 and E_4 energies), it is possible that such interactions would not manifest outside of the compacted spaces of level 3 and above, which could explain why such interactions (if they exist) have not yet been identified. And, for the supposed interaction resulting from lateral displacement of E_3 energy onto level 3, it is possible that any of its effects which *do* manifest have been confused/conflated with aspects of the strong interaction.

⁶It should thus be apparent that use of the term “graviton” in this paper does not imply any bias towards a *quantized* conception of gravity.

⁷Some articles that question the need for quantum gravity are [16] and [17].

Finally, there is “backward displacement onto *level 0*”, which will be taken up in sections 5.3 and 5.5.

4.9.6 A possible connection between nonforward displacements and gauge symmetries

As described above, the *backward* displacements take energy at an initial level and place it at a *prior* level, which (by postulate 4) is *independent of* the initial level. Such an independence relation might inject one or more symmetries into a description of the process. Some clues are as follows.

We have found that, in the process of backward displacing energy onto a prior level, some dimensionalities are *reduced*. For example, the electromagnetic interaction, due to the backward displacement of E_2 energy onto level 1, yields the photon; and leaves the photon experiencing two dimensions, or degrees of freedom. However, an observer at level 2 (or above) still sees the photon as existing within *four-dimensional* space-time; thus, to this observer, there are two *redundant* degrees of freedom for the photon. Such redundancy may be related to, or even constitute, the gauge symmetry of the electromagnetic interaction [18].

On the other hand, for the process of *lateral/intralevel* displacement of energy (such as the one to which we attributed the weak interaction), there may be less symmetry involved; i.e., since the destination level for the energy is the *same* as the initial level, then no interlevel independence relations and/or dimensional redundancies (like the ones generated in backward displacement) would occur. This result might augment our understanding of the so-called “broken symmetry” that is associated with the weak interaction.

4.10 Interaction examples

In our descriptions of fundamental interactions above we actually only provided an account of the first *half* of some interactions: *emission* of the mediating particle from its source, by either backward or lateral displacement. In the examples below, we give more complete descriptions by also including (where appropriate) the *absorption* of the mediating object.

4.10.1 Electromagnetic

Consider the electromagnetic interaction between an electron and a proton, in which the electron emits a photon, and the proton absorbs it. Our description of the electromagnetic interaction in section 4.9.1 accounted only for the first half of that interaction: emission of the photon by the electron, which we described as the backward displacement of E_2 energy onto level 1.

The second half of the interaction – absorption of the photon by the proton – can be accounted for as follows: the photon energy, at level 1, is *forward* displaced⁸ from level 1 (i.e.

⁸This kind of “forward” displacement is different from the forward displacements that *create* the fundamental sequence ($\mathbf{d}_0, \mathbf{d}_1, \mathbf{d}_2, \mathbf{d}_3$) for the system. This will be clarified as we go along, and then summarized/formalized in postulate 5 (section 4.14).

along the line of \mathbf{d}_1), thereby becoming associated with (i.e. “absorbed by”) the \mathbf{d}_1 component of the *proton’s* E_2 energy.

Such emission and absorption processes imply that *only* objects having E_2 energy can participate (as emitters or absorbers) in the electromagnetic interaction; which, again, indicates that electric charge is associated with E_2 energy (or, more strongly, E_2 energy is at least a necessary precursor for electric charge).

Speaking of which, since no one has ever defined what “electric charge” actually is [19], then let us try our hand at formulating a fundamental definition of it, according to the present model:

Electric charge is defined as: (a) E_2 energy that can be backward displaced onto level 1 as a photon; and (b) E_2 energy whose \mathbf{d}_1 component is capable of absorbing a photon.

We note that this definition of electric charge comports with the minimalist notion (described in section 4.4.7) that all physical properties should be reducible to just *energy and its different arrangements, relations, and behaviors*.

Now, according to the present model, *neutrinos* must possess E_2 energy (since neutrinos are a source of the weak interaction, and that interaction involves lateral displacement of E_2 energy). But neutrinos are known to have *zero* electric charge (and are thought to have no internal structure). Apparently, then, the presence of E_2 energy is necessary, but not sufficient, for an object to have electric charge (and thus to participate as an emitter or absorber in the electromagnetic interaction).

Using the definition of electric charge above, we can reformulate the statement “neutrinos have zero electric charge” as: A neutrino’s E_2 energy is unable to be backward displaced onto level 1 as a photon; and the \mathbf{d}_1 component of a neutrino’s E_2 energy is unable to absorb a photon. Such inabilities of a neutrino’s E_2 energy might be caused by something that neutrinos are missing due to a quirk of their provenance.

4.10.2 Weak

Consider the decay of a neutron into a proton via the weak interaction, mediated by emission of a W^- particle (so-called beta decay). From our results above, this process is described as follows: E_2 energy associated with the neutron is *laterally* displaced onto/within level 2, as the W^- particle – thereby transforming the neutron into a proton.

As another example, the weak interaction between a proton (emitter) and electron (absorber), mediated by exchange of a Z particle, is described as follows: E_2 energy associated with the proton is laterally displaced within level 2 (as the Z particle), which then becomes associated with (absorbed by) the *electron’s* E_2 energy.

4.10.3 Strong

The strong interaction between *nucleons* A (emitter) and B (absorber), mediated by exchange of a meson, can be described in the following way: E_3 energy associated with A is backward

displaced onto level 2, as a meson. This meson energy then becomes associated with (absorbed by) the \mathbf{d}_2 component of B 's E_3 energy, which forward displaces it along the line of \mathbf{d}_2 .

The strong interaction between *quarks* A and B , mediated by exchange of a gluon, can be described as follows: E_3 energy associated with A is backward displaced onto level 1 as a gluon, via the sequence $(-\mathbf{d}_2, -\mathbf{d}_1)$. This gluon energy is then forward displaced along the lines of \mathbf{d}_1 and \mathbf{d}_2 – i.e. via the sequence $(\mathbf{d}_1, \mathbf{d}_2)$ – thereby becoming absorbed by the \mathbf{d}_2 component of B 's E_3 energy.

4.10.4 Gravitational

Consider two entities/particles A and B at level 1 or above. The *gravity- A* interaction between them (where A is the emitter, and B is the absorber) is described as follows: E_1 energy associated with A is laterally displaced onto/within level 1 (as the graviton), which then becomes absorbed by B 's E_1 energy.

4.11 A scheme for producing matter-antimatter asymmetry

We have found that the fundamental sequence of displacements, $(\mathbf{d}_0, \mathbf{d}_1, \mathbf{d}_2, \mathbf{d}_3)$, produces E_2 energy at level 2 and above, and E_3 energy at level 3 and above (section 4.2). And recall that E_2 energy and E_3 energy are associated with the production of electric charge and baryon charge, respectively (section 4.6).

In constructing the fundamental sequence, let us now suppose the following pattern of electric and baryon charge production: At their native levels, E_2 energy and E_3 energy produce their respective charges with a particular sign, either positive or negative (+/–). At the next subsequent level, they produce charges of the *opposite* sign. And at further subsequent levels they produce charges of *zero*. Or, in short: The charge associated with each of these energy types *alternates* in sign for the first two levels at which the energy type is in effect, and is zero at later levels. Note that this electric- and baryon-charge production scheme is *nonconservative* at each of the first two respective steps in the process (but might be conservative overall).

Thus, the electric charge (associated with E_2 energy) that is produced at level 2 has, let us say, *negative* sign; the electric charge produced at level 3 has *positive* sign; and the electric charge produced at level 4 and above is zero. Likewise, the baryon charge (associated with E_3 energy) that is produced at level 3 has, let us say, positive sign; the baryon charge produced at level 4 has negative sign; and the baryon charge produced at level 5 and above (if any) is zero.

The result of this pattern of charge production would be leptons with negative electric charge at level 2 (which, after decays, yield *electrons*); baryons with positive electric charge and positive baryon charge at level 3 (which yield *protons*); and objects at level 4 (let's call them *transbaryons*) that have *zero* electric charge and negative baryon charge. The transbaryons at level 4, having zero electric charge, are thus candidates for *dark matter*. These results, as illustrated in Fig. 3, produce a world without antimatter (i.e., matter-antimatter *asymmetry*) – which comports with the world that we currently observe.

In summary, our basic paradigm for constructing the physical universe (via a sequence of discrete displacements), together with the above-supposed scheme of charge production at each step of the process, offers a simple way to generate the observed matter-antimatter asymmetry, while also yielding a new candidate for dark matter.

Fig. 3: The spectrum of particles that the fundamental displacement sequence ($\mathbf{d}_0, \mathbf{d}_1, \mathbf{d}_2, \mathbf{d}_3$) would yield, given the pattern of alternating-sign-then-zero charge production that we have supposed. This particle spectrum comports with observed matter-antimatter asymmetry. And level 4 yields a new candidate for dark matter.

4.12 Primary and secondary displacements

In contrast to the nonconservative charge-production scheme described above, our present-day experience is that *all* electric- and baryon-charge production is *fully* conservative. Consideration of this, as well as our model of the fundamental interactions developed above, in which some displacements of energy propagate “along the lines of” other, *already-existing* displacements, suggests the existence of two general categories of displacement, which will be called *primary* and *secondary* – defined as follows:

- The *primary displacements* are the ones that construct the *infrastructure* of the system, the sequence for which we have denoted as ($\mathbf{d}_0, \mathbf{d}_1, \mathbf{d}_2, \mathbf{d}_3$). That is, starting at level 0, the primary displacements construct the subsequent levels (1, 2, 3, 4) and the connections between them; and relations between these displacements construct the different spaces of the system (as described in section 3).

In addition, the primary displacements input energy into the levels that they construct, thereby producing dark energy at level 1, the Higgs field at level 2, the initial population of leptons and baryons at levels 2 and 3, respectively, and (possibly) transbaryons/dark matter at level 4. In our scheme of matter-antimatter asymmetry, the primary displacements \mathbf{d}_1 and \mathbf{d}_2 (and/or their corresponding energy types, E_2 and E_3) do not

respect electric- and baryon-charge conservation (they might also not respect, e.g., lepton-charge conservation).

The primary displacements are all *forward* displacements.

- The *secondary displacements* may be forward, backward, or lateral/intralevel. These are the displacements that happen once the necessary infrastructure of the universe has been constructed/established by the sequence of primary displacements.

Examples of secondary displacements include the nonforward (i.e. backward and lateral/intralevel) ones that we have described (in section 4.9) as being responsible for the emission phases of the fundamental interactions; and the forward ones that are involved in the absorption phases of some of those interactions (section 4.10).

Pair production offers other examples of secondary-forward displacement. For example, the creation of an electron-positron pair from a photon can be described as the secondary-forward displacement of the photon energy along the line of \mathbf{d}_1 , from level 1 to level 2. Similarly, the creation of a proton-antiproton pair from a photon can be described as the secondary-forward displacement of the photon energy along the sequence $(\mathbf{d}_1, \mathbf{d}_2)$, from level 1 to level 3.

In essence, the secondary displacements utilize the *existing* infrastructure (of levels, and the primary displacements that connect the levels) as a kind of interaction *network* – moving energy in all directions (forward, backward, and lateral). In this respect, the levels and primary displacements act as *nodes* and *edges*, respectively, in a *communication network*.

Evidently, the secondary displacements (which comprise all of the fundamental interactions) are *fully conservative* of electric and baryon charge.

We use the same notation for the secondary-*forward* displacements as for the primary displacements; i.e. $\mathbf{d}_0, \mathbf{d}_1, \mathbf{d}_2$, etc. When using these symbols, either the context or explicit statements will tell us whether they represent the primary or secondary type. For the *backward* displacements (which are *always* secondary), we use the notation developed for them in section 4.9; i.e., $-\mathbf{d}_0, -\mathbf{d}_1, -\mathbf{d}_2$, etc. And for lateral/intralevel displacements (which, too, are always secondary), there is no special notation yet developed.

In summary, primary displacements are about *constructing* the infrastructure of a *new* system or world, and priming it with energy. Secondary displacements are about what happens within that *already-existing* infrastructure. Both primary and secondary displacements communicate energy among the levels. However, the primary displacements only communicate in *one* direction – *forward*; whereas the secondary displacements may communicate in *all* directions: forward, backward, and lateral. So, to be clear, the primary displacements do not just disappear after their initial creation; rather, they remain operant, and form an infrastructure backbone that also acts as a system of communication *channels* along which the secondary displacements can propagate.

4.13 Making sense of the displacement types

A displacement type in the system can be designated by selecting *one* term from each of the following two groups of displacement characteristics (with some restrictions, noted below):

1. Primary; secondary.
2. Forward; backward; lateral/intralevel. (Called the *direction*.)

Thus, the designation of a specific displacement type is given by a *doublet* of these terms, such as: primary-forward, secondary-backward, secondary-forward, or secondary-lateral.

Note, however, that the type designation “primary-forward” is actually redundant, since, as stated earlier, all primary displacements *are* forward (i.e. there is no such thing as a *backward* primary displacement); so this designation can be stated equivalently as just “primary”. Likewise, all backward displacements are necessarily *secondary* displacements (since backward displacements *do not* create new infrastructure of edges/lines and nodes; rather, they propagate along *existing* lines, and onto *existing* levels/nodes); so, for example, the designation “secondary-backward” is equivalent to just “backward”. And all lateral displacements are secondary; so, for example, the designation “secondary-lateral” is equivalent to just “lateral”.

4.14 Postulates 5 and 6

Recent developments in the model suggest the need for two more postulates:

Postulate 5: Within the infrastructure of levels and primary displacements (shown in Fig. 1), *secondary* displacements may be propagated in all directions (backward, forward, and lateral/intralevel).

Postulate 6: A displacement of any type, to a given level, involves the input/communication of energy onto that level, which constitutes an object/entity (e.g. a “particle”) at that level.

5 Constructing position, velocity, acceleration, and spin properties

As concluded in section 4.8, \mathbf{d}_0 's independence from ordinary space causes a particle's default location to be *everywhere in space*. Nevertheless, it is evident (all around us) that a particle can also acquire a (more or less) definite position property within ordinary space. In addition, particles also have the properties of velocity, acceleration, and spin. We outline below how these properties are constructed in the present model.

5.1 Position

We have already described how \mathbf{d}_0 “looks” from the perspective of \mathbf{d}_1 : as an isotropic, homogeneous three-dimensional space (i.e. ordinary space). We now ask, how does \mathbf{d}_0 look from the perspective of (an observer at) *level 0*? The answer (by postulate 3) is simply that \mathbf{d}_0 is a *one-dimensional vector*. Furthermore, by the scope rule, this interpretation/meaning of \mathbf{d}_0 (from the perspective of level 0) is available *everywhere* within ordinary space.

Consider now an observing object/particle A at *level 2* or above (e.g. an electron or proton), which thus has, at minimum, \mathbf{d}_0 and \mathbf{d}_1 in its sequence/genome. Consider also an observed object B at *level 1* or above (e.g. a photon, electron, or proton); i.e. an object that has, at minimum, \mathbf{d}_0 in its genome. In general, A ’s \mathbf{d}_1 component sees \mathbf{d}_0 as ordinary, isotropic, homogeneous three-dimensional space; and, specifically, it sees B ’s \mathbf{d}_0 component (and therefore B itself, as per section 4.8) as being smeared uniformly throughout this space – and thus, in this sense, having every possible position within ordinary space, but no particular position. In other words, from the perspective of A ’s \mathbf{d}_1 component, object B is a *uniform field* that fills all of space.

By the scope rule, however, the meaning of B ’s \mathbf{d}_0 component *from the perspective of level 0* is also available to object A ; to wit, from this perspective, A sees B ’s \mathbf{d}_0 component as a *one-dimensional vector*. With the results of section 4.8 in mind, we interpret that this meaning of \mathbf{d}_0 is just the *position vector* of B with respect to A ; that is, the position vector of B **relative to** A .

Since A is *any* object at level 2 or above, then *every* object at level 2 or above generates a relative position vector for B in the same way. And since B is *any* object at level 1 or above, then relative position vectors are generated in this way for *every* object at level 1 or above. In general, a relative position vector so constructed may be denoted by the symbol \mathbf{r}_{d0} , where the “d0” in the subscript indicates that this construction depends on the presence of the displacement \mathbf{d}_0 in the genome of object B . In the language of Zurek et al., we might also call \mathbf{r}_{d0} the *fundamental position pointer* for object B , with respect to A . Moreover, if the set of all observing objects such as A constitutes the “environment”, then some combination of all the \mathbf{r}_{d0} -pointers so constructed might yield the fundamental “pointer basis” [20–22].

Since \mathbf{r}_{d0} is the position vector of B **relative to** A , then different objects/observers A at level 2 or above will construct different relative position vectors for B , with (generally) *different* magnitudes (*distances*). In other words, these observers will validly *disagree* about the distance to B .

Given that the construction of a *relative* position vector for an object depends on that object having a \mathbf{d}_0 component in its sequence/genome, then, for an object/entity that *lacks* a \mathbf{d}_0 component (i.e. an entity at level 0), the construction of a relative position vector cannot occur, and so the position of such an object will presumably be *absolute*, not relative (i.e., all observers A will *agree* on the distance to B). This result is supported by the following analysis, which stems from asking the question: From the perspective of an observer at level 2 (or above), what is the “position” of an object/entity at level 0?

Let us use the symbol \mathbf{r}_{L0} to refer to the hypothetical position vector for an object at level 0. To sort out the nature of \mathbf{r}_{L0} we note that, due to the scope rule, an entity at level

0 is operant *throughout* the system; which implies that the “position” of such an object is *everywhere* within the ordinary space of the system/world – and so the “distance” to that object is effectively *zero*. That is, *all* observers at level 2 or above will *agree* that the distance to an object/entity at level 0 is exactly *zero*. It follows that the *magnitude/length* of \mathbf{r}_{L0} (being zero from the perspective of *all* observers at level 2 or above) is *not* relative – rather, it is *absolute*.

In summary, from the perspective of an observer at level 2 or above, an object at level 1 or above (i.e. an object that possesses a \mathbf{d}_0 component in its sequence/genome) has a *relative* position vector, whose magnitude (distance) is typically *different* for each observer – and so that distance is a *relative* quantity. In contrast, every object/observer at level 2 or above agrees that the distance to an entity at level 0 (which *lacks* a \mathbf{d}_0 component in its genome) is *zero* – and so that distance is an *absolute* quantity. In other words, *relative* distance is only supported for objects *at level 1 or above* (where \mathbf{d}_0 is operant); *below* level 1 (where \mathbf{d}_0 is *not* operant), distance is *absolute*.

5.2 Spin

In the above analysis, the relative position vector (i.e. the position vector of B with respect to A) is constructed when A refers to the (perspective of the) observer at level 0 to interpret the meaning of B 's \mathbf{d}_0 component.

Likewise, object B can (without help from A) refer to the observer at level 0 to interpret the meaning of its *own* \mathbf{d}_0 component. The result, again, is that \mathbf{d}_0 is a one-dimensional vector. However, since this interpretation of \mathbf{d}_0 (as a one-dimensional vector) is *not* relative to another object (A) within the system/world, then it will yield a property that appears to be *intrinsic* to B . To wit, it should yield an intrinsic or internal axis, and orientation, for object B . Since B is *any* object at level 1 or above, then *every* object at level 1 or above will have such an internal axis. We interpret this internal axis and orientation to be the property known as *spin*.

Why, according to the present model, some objects/particles have half-integral spin (i.e. fermions) and others have integral spin (i.e. bosons) is not yet clear, but the following is likely to be an important clue: In the present model, the primary creation of fermions occurs via *forward* displacement, whereas the creation of bosons occurs via *nonforward* displacement.

5.3 Velocity

Let us now move on to the succeeding displacement, \mathbf{d}_1 , and ask: What is the meaning of that displacement from the perspective of (an observer at) level 0? The answer is that (like \mathbf{d}_0) it is a one-dimensional vector, and (due to the scope rule) this meaning of \mathbf{d}_1 is available throughout ordinary space.

Now consider two objects, A and B , *both at level 2 or above* (e.g. electrons or protons), which thus have (at minimum) \mathbf{d}_0 and \mathbf{d}_1 components in their genomes. By the scope rule, the meaning of B 's \mathbf{d}_1 component from the perspective of *level 0* is available to object A ;

to wit, from that perspective, A sees B 's \mathbf{d}_1 component as a *one-dimensional vector*. But what property should be associated with this \mathbf{d}_1 vector? Since \mathbf{d}_1 is subsequent to \mathbf{d}_0 , then object A may see \mathbf{d}_1 as being logically “attached” to the end of the relative position vector associated with \mathbf{d}_0 (i.e. \mathbf{r}_{d0}) – which evokes the image from classical mechanics of the *velocity vector* of an object being attached to the end of its position vector, thereby suggesting that the property of *velocity* might be associated with \mathbf{d}_1 . This association is further supported by the following argument.

As indicated in section 4.3, the property of *action* is native to level 2. At that level, only the displacements \mathbf{d}_0 and \mathbf{d}_1 are operant. And we have just associated \mathbf{d}_0 (from the perspective of level 0) with the position property. So, in order to yield action at level 2, it is suggested that \mathbf{d}_1 (from that same perspective) be associated with momentum, and thus with velocity.

We therefore interpret that the meaning of B 's \mathbf{d}_1 component, as seen by A (applying the perspective of level 0), is just the *velocity vector* of B with respect to A ; that is, the velocity vector of B **relative to** A – which may be denoted as \mathbf{v}_{d1} , where the “d1” in the subscript indicates that the construction of this vector depends on the presence of the displacement \mathbf{d}_1 in the genome of object B . Since A is *any* object at level 2 or above, then *every* such object generates a relative velocity vector (\mathbf{v}_{d1}) for B in the same way. And since B is *any* object at level 2 or above (i.e., any object having a \mathbf{d}_1 component), then relative velocity vectors/ \mathbf{v}_{d1} 's are generated in this way for *every* such object.

Due to the *relative* nature of the velocity vectors so constructed, different objects/observers A will construct *different* \mathbf{v}_{d1} velocity vectors for B , with (generally) *different* magnitudes/speeds. Thus, different observers A may validly *disagree* about the speed of B . Indeed, any two leptons or baryons (level-2 and level-3 objects, respectively, in the present model; which both therefore have \mathbf{d}_1 components) *do* see each other as having relative speed.

On the other hand, given that the construction of a *relative* velocity vector for an object depends on that object having a \mathbf{d}_1 component in its genome, then, for an object/entity B that *lacks* a \mathbf{d}_1 component (i.e. an object at levels 0 or 1), the construction of a relative velocity vector cannot occur, and so all observers A (at level 2 or above) will *agree* on the *same* speed for B ; that is, the speed of B will be *absolute*, not relative.

Relative velocity is thus only supported for objects *at level 2 or above* (where \mathbf{d}_1 is operant). Hence, for objects at levels 0 and 1, which lack \mathbf{d}_1 in their genome, *there is no relative velocity/speed*. Indeed, the *photon* is a level-1 object in the present model, and is known to have absolute speed (the speed of light, c); likewise, the graviton and gluons are level-1 objects, and are thought to have absolute speed, with the same nonzero value as the photon.

Furthermore, dark energy is another level-1 entity in the present model, and so we predict that its speed is also *absolute*; i.e., that all observers (A) at level 2 or above will *agree* on the value of its speed. However, in this case that speed is likely to be *zero*.

Why should dark energy have an absolute speed of zero, while other level-1 objects (photon, gluon and graviton) have a *nonzero* absolute speed? To answer this, we must recall that (in the present model) fundamental forces, and thus *accelerations*, are the product of

nonforward displacements (i.e. backward and lateral/intralevel displacements). But the process of creating dark energy, it may be recalled, involves only the *forward* displacement \mathbf{d}_0 – so there is no possibility in that process of accelerating dark energy to a finite speed; and so its speed is zero.⁹ In contrast, it may be recalled that the processes of creating the photon, gluon and graviton (the latter, to be further elaborated in section 6) all involve *nonforward* displacements, which yield accelerations, and thus *nonzero* speeds.

We can also ask: Why is the speed of light (and gluons, gravitons) a *constant*? Answer: Because nonforward displacements are necessarily involved *only* in the photon’s *creation*, not in the aftermath of its creation. If nonforward displacements do somehow become involved in the aftermath, then acceleration can occur and the situation becomes *noninertial*, in which case the speed of the photon might *not* be constant. The same applies to dark energy: its speed remains constant (at zero), as long as nonforward displacements have no involvement in the aftermath of its creation (a situation which might *always* hold true).

In summary:

The construction of *relative* speed for an object depends on that object having a \mathbf{d}_1 component in its genome. Indeed, objects such as the electron and proton, being level-2 and level-3 objects, respectively, *have* a \mathbf{d}_1 component in their genomes, and thus have relative speed. The photon, however, being a level-1 object, *lacks* a \mathbf{d}_1 component in its genome, and so can only have *absolute* speed.

The photon’s speed is *nonzero* because a nonforward displacement is involved in its creation, which yields acceleration during that process. (In contrast, the speed of dark energy, while also absolute, is likely to be zero, because its creation is due solely to the *forward* displacement \mathbf{d}_0 .)

Once a photon is created with its nonzero speed, only the subsequent involvement of nonforward displacements (and thus forces/accelerations) can *change* that speed; in the absence of those (i.e., if the situation remains *inertial*), the speed of the photon will be a *constant*.

The present model thereby provides a kind of *genetic* explanation for (or *derivation of*) the second postulate of special relativity: The genome for light is missing the \mathbf{d}_1 “gene” that is necessary for relative speed; so the speed of light cannot be relative, and must therefore be absolute.

Finally, we ask, what is the speed of an object at *level 0*? Let us use the symbols \mathbf{v}_{L0} and \mathbf{v}_{L1} to denote the velocity vectors for objects at levels 0 and 1, respectively.

We have already made the case that the speed $|\mathbf{v}_{L1}|$ of a level-1 object is absolute, and that its value is nonzero if it was created with *nonforward* displacement (as for photons, gluons, and gravitons), but is zero if the object was created with *forward* displacement (as for dark energy). We now make a similar case for the speed $|\mathbf{v}_{L0}|$ of a *level-0* object/entity.

⁹An alternative derivation of zero speed for dark energy is as follows: Since dark energy is a *single* entity spanning all of ordinary space, and indeed it is the energy of space itself, then it cannot really move *within* that space – and so its speed is zero.

First, consider a level-0 object that is created via a process of backward (nonforward) displacement from level 1 or above. Because the process originates at level 1 or above, then it has a \mathbf{d}_0 component, and thus has a position vector within ordinary space relative to observers at level 2 or above (section 5.1). Due to the scope rule, however, the resulting level-0 object is *instantly* operant/available *everywhere* in space; so all observers at level 2 or above will *agree* that its speed for that process is *infinite* (and thus nonzero). Hence, if we account for the process that creates it, the speed of such a level-0 object is absolute, and *nonzero*.

Now let us consider a “bare” level-0 object (i.e., we either ignore its creation process, or assume that nonforward displacements are not involved in that process). Due to the scope rule, an entity at level 0 is operant *throughout* ordinary space, which implies that the “position” of such an object is effectively *all of space*. Since its position is everywhere in space, then such an entity does not travel or propagate from one point in space to another – for, *it is already there*. It follows that all observers (at level 2 or above) will *agree* that its speed is zero. The speed of a “bare” level-0 object/entity is thus absolute, and *zero*.

5.4 Acceleration

Now, for the succeeding displacement, \mathbf{d}_2 , we ask: What is the meaning of that displacement from the perspective of (an observer at) level 0? As usual, from that perspective, \mathbf{d}_2 is a one-dimensional vector; so, following the pattern above, it is suggested that we associate this meaning of \mathbf{d}_2 with a *relative acceleration* vector.

However, as indicated earlier (section 4.4.7), the properties associated with an object’s \mathbf{d}_2 component are *confined* within the *internal* spaces of that object; and so the relative acceleration associated with \mathbf{d}_2 is also confined or “hidden” within the interior spaces of objects at level 3 or above, such as the proton. It follows that, *outside* of those internal spaces, i.e. *within the ordinary space of our direct experience* (which coincides with the “standard perspective”), the relative acceleration associated with \mathbf{d}_2 will not manifest, and so *all* acceleration within that realm will be *absolute*, not relative. Indeed, in our direct experience all observers *do agree* on the value of an object’s physical acceleration (as measured by an accelerometer), and so that acceleration *is* absolute.

As with the position and velocity properties discussed above, for the situation in which the acceleration is always absolute (i.e., within the ordinary space of our direct experience), the *magnitude/value* of the acceleration can be either nonzero or zero, depending on whether or not nonforward displacements (i.e. “forces”) are involved. When they are *not* involved, the acceleration will be *zero*, and will remain a *constant* at that value. When they *are* involved, the acceleration can be *nonzero*, and its value may be a variable. But this result is just the law of inertia, or Newton’s first law of motion (have we just *derived* it?).

5.5 Backward displacement onto level 0

In section 5.3, we concluded that an entity created by backward displacement onto level 0 becomes *instantly* operant/available *everywhere* in space; so, in this sense, its speed is *infinite*. It is proposed, therefore, that backward displacement onto level 0 produces *instantaneous* interaction/communication within the physical universe. Of course, it is just such an interaction that is needed to explain what happens in the quantum “collapse” phenomena, where the values of properties are instantaneously correlated across space – e.g., in EPR/entanglement-type experiments (more on this in section 5.6).

Just as backward displacement onto *level 1* may be a feature of all E_j -energy forms that are native to level 2 or above (i.e. E_2 energy, E_3 energy, etc.), so also backward displacement onto *level 0* may be a feature of all E_j -energy forms that are native to *level 1* or above (which is to say, *all* E_j -energy forms within the system – i.e. E_1 energy, E_2 energy, E_3 energy, etc.). In this respect, instantaneous interaction via backward displacement onto level 0 might be a universal mode of communication, performed by *all* E_j -energy types.

Backward displacement of E_1 , E_2 , and E_3 energies *onto level 0* may be denoted by $-\mathbf{d}_0$, $(-\mathbf{d}_1, -\mathbf{d}_0)$, and $(-\mathbf{d}_2, -\mathbf{d}_1, -\mathbf{d}_0)$, respectively.

An interaction via backward displacement onto level 0 may thus be described as follows: E_j energy associated with object A is backward displaced onto level 0, producing an object/entity at that level. Due to the scope rule, this object is then universally and instantaneously operant throughout all of ordinary space.

5.6 Aspects of constructing definite values for properties; classicality and classical *precedence*

Recall that object A 's \mathbf{d}_1 component sees object B 's \mathbf{d}_0 component (and thus B itself) as being spread out across ordinary space.

But the view of B 's \mathbf{d}_0 component from the perspective of *level 0* may then be used by A to construct a position vector for B (relative to A). Likewise, the view of \mathbf{d}_0 from level 0 also yields the *spin* property of objects, and the view of \mathbf{d}_1 from level 0 yields relative velocity/speed. The common denominator here is that the construction of each of these properties requires *the perspective/view from level 0*.

Given that level 0 is prior to everything else in the system, then its view of \mathbf{d}_0 has greater priority (and *precedence*) than the *subsequent* view of \mathbf{d}_0 from the perspective of \mathbf{d}_1 . Such precedence presumably means that the view of \mathbf{d}_0 from level 0 can *override* (*overwrite*?) the smearing out that occurs from the perspective of \mathbf{d}_1 , and thus may be used to construct a *definite* position for an object that has a \mathbf{d}_0 component. This apparently explains (at least in part) how the position of an object can initially be *all of space*, and then “collapse” down to a definite point in space.

Generalizing this result, the *priority* of the view of \mathbf{d}_0 and \mathbf{d}_1 *from level 0* enables construction of a world in which objects can have *definite* position, speed, and spin – i.e. the *classical* world. That the classical world is rooted in a process that has greater priority/precedence

presumably explains why it manifests as more real, robust, and “fundamental”¹⁰ than the fuzzy/smeared-out “quantum” world. Indeed, we might say that the priority/precedence of the perspective from level 0 yields classicality and *classical precedence*.

Given its precedence, however, if the view from level 0 were *sufficient* to cause collapse by itself, then every object in the universe would likely have a definite position, speed, or spin *by default*. But we know (e.g. from the double-slit and entanglement experiments) that this is not the case. Indeed, the default seems to be that an object *does not* have definite values of those properties, but *can acquire them via interaction with a “measuring apparatus”*. This leads us to conclude that the view from level 0 is *necessary*, but not sufficient, to give an object a definite position, velocity, or spin within ordinary space.

It is easy to see why the view from level 0 would be insufficient to establish definite values for those properties: Ordinary space is only operant *at level 2 and above*, so positions, speeds, and orientations within that space only have meaning at those levels. The observer at *level 0* therefore “knows” nothing (i.e. is agnostic/unknowing) about positions, speeds, and orientations within ordinary space, and thus cannot *by itself* assign meaningful values to them. The process of assigning values to those properties therefore requires the participation/input of an object/observer, *A*, *at level 2 or above*, for which (in the context of operant ordinary space) positions, speeds, and orientations within ordinary space *do* have meaning. Such an observer (*A*) constitutes “the measuring apparatus”, in whole or in part.

The construction of position, velocity, and spin properties, *and* their values, is thus a *co-creation* process involving the observer at level 0 *and* at least one observer at level 2 or above (i.e. the measuring apparatus). Nevertheless, it is still the priority/precedence of the view from level 0 that enables the “collapse” phenomena to occur, allowing classical definiteness to override/overwrite (and take precedence over) the default fuzziness. Moreover, the fact that the observer at level 0 is independent of, and unknowing about, ordinary space and time might account for the randomness and probabilistic aspects that accompany such “measurement” processes.

As an example of how the process might work, consider two interacting objects *A* and *B* (where *A* is the observing object, at level 2 or above; and *B* is the observed object, at level 1 or above). First, *A*’s \mathbf{d}_1 component sees *B*’s \mathbf{d}_0 component (and thus *B* itself) as being smeared out across all of space. Second, *A* uses the perspective of level 0 to interpret *B*’s \mathbf{d}_0 component as an *indefinite* relative position vector (or *pointer* – the *fundamental* pointer for *B* with respect to *A*). Third, the *interaction* between *A* and *B* causes *A* to *construct* information about *B*’s distance, speed, and orientation variables. Fourth, object *A* then uses that information to *assign values* to *B*’s variables, via the following process: *A* passes the constructed information about *B* to (the observer at) level 0, which then writes/records those values – thereby constructing, e.g., a *definite* position vector for *B* with respect to *A*. Given that the scope of the observer at level 0 is universal and instantaneous, then all other observers at level 2 or above will instantly *agree* on the results; e.g., that *B* has a certain position within ordinary space.

Note that object *A* (by itself) *does not* have the needed scope to *write/record* a value for

¹⁰According to Zurek’s interpretation of Bohr [20, 22].

B 's position variable (or *any* of B 's variables); rather, A must pass the constructed position information to the observer at level 0, which *does* have the scope to write/record values. The position information is likely passed to the observer at level 0 via *backward displacement onto level 0*, which (as described in section 5.5) acts instantaneously across all of space, and is able to not only write a “1” (present) at a particular location, but also to write “0” (not present) at all other locations, thereby bringing about “collapse” at all locations except one. Moreover, the time-independence of the observer at level 0 may account for its ability to write values (e.g., in delayed-choice experiments) in defiance of the normal temporal ordering of events as seen from the perspective of observers (like you and me) at level 2 or above.

As another example, consider the construction of definite spins for entangled objects B_1 and B_2 (both of which are at level 1 or above). First, *indefinite* spins are constructed for both B_1 and B_2 when these objects refer to the view of their \mathbf{d}_0 components from the perspective of level 0 (as described in section 5.2). The spins are indefinite (i.e., not married to any particular direction in space) at this stage because, as described above, the observer at level 0 is unknowing/agnostic about directions within ordinary space. Next, object B_1 interacts with an observing object A (which is at level 2 or above, and constitutes the measuring apparatus, in whole or in part). Via this interaction, object A constructs orientation information for B_1 , and passes it (via backward displacement) to the observer at level 0, which writes a definite orientation/direction for the spin of B_1 – say, spin “up”. Given the universal scope of the observer at level 0, it also instantaneously writes spin “down” for object B_2 , irrespective of the distance between B_1 and B_2 (indeed, the observer at level 0 does not even “see” the distance between B_1 and B_2 , since ordinary space is only operant for observers *at level 2 and above*).

Clearly, then, the observer at level 0 is not constrained by the space and time relations (and intervals) between objects and events that seem so important and imposing for observers (like you and me) at level 2 and above. Rather, that observer only sees *logical* relations – and is thus analogous to the CPU of a computer, or the kernel of its operating system, neither of which knows anything about the spatiotemporal effects that may be output to the screen for a running application program, but which nevertheless perform underlying logical operations that are needed to generate those effects. This analogy is expanded in the next subsection.

In summary, if the present model is basically correct, then the above analysis might constitute new advances into the problems and processes that typically come under the rubric of “quantum measurement”. However, more detail and clarity about those processes is still needed.

5.7 An analogy from computing

The processes described above – by which objects acquire properties with definite values – might have a ring of familiarity for readers who have some background in computer science or programming. This is because there is a strong analogy between the two, as follows.

In a compiled programming language, variables and their types are *declared* during compilation, and *assigned* values during run time. Thus, suppose B is an object within an application program that is running under the operating system *kernel*. The application

program (e.g. a word processor, spreadsheet, web browser, video player, etc.) does not have the scope to write values for B 's variables directly to memory; rather, it must initiate a *system call* to the operating system kernel (which *does* have the needed scope) to write those values. The value to be assigned is included in the system call as an *argument*, and it is written/recorded by means of the kernel placing that value in the memory location/cell that was allocated for that B variable during compilation.

Now, in the present model, suppose that B is an object at level 1 or above, and that the view of one of B 's displacement components (e.g. \mathbf{d}_0 or \mathbf{d}_1) from the perspective of level 0 merely “declares” a corresponding variable and its type (e.g., relative position, relative velocity, or spin), without assigning a value to it. The “variable” is then assigned an actual value via interactions with the measurement apparatus that occur during “run time”. Specifically, an object A (constituting the measurement apparatus, in whole or in part) can initiate the assignment of a value to one of B 's variables, but does not have the necessary scope to actually *write* it. The observer at level 0 (the “kernel”), however, *does* have the necessary scope. Thus, A 's assignment of a value to a B variable is basically a “system call” to the observer at level 0 to write or record that value/argument. As previously indicated, the basic mechanism/interaction by which such system calls/assignments are performed is likely *backward displacement onto level 0*, since that interaction acts instantaneously across ordinary space.

The strength of this analogy is increased by the fact that the scope, nesting, and inheritance rules of the present model are also operant in computer programs. Indeed, they seem to be features of systems that perform logical derivations or computations in general, including the most prevalent one: the system known as Natural Deduction, or ND (to wit, “subproofs” in ND are nested within prior “scope levels”, and inherit everything from them [23]). [24, 25]

Thus, we may place the present model for constructing the physical universe (which we dubbed “system P” in the introduction) into a common category with computer programs – i.e., systems of logical derivation and construction. In other words, the process for constructing the physical universe seems to follow the form of a logical derivation. Which echoes John Archibald Wheeler’s intuition about “the basic operating principle of the universe”, or the “pregeometry”:

What else can pregeometry be ... than the calculus of propositions? [26]

Indeed, the most parsimonious way to create a universe that is *logical* (and therefore comprehensible) might be to create it as an instance of logical form itself.¹¹

¹¹This statement has an *a priori* argument in its favor, as follows.

Suppose we accept the following two propositions:

1. The process for constructing/deriving the universe must be the **simplest possible** process (we might call this the *maximum parsimony requirement*).
2. The process must be comprehensible.

To be comprehensible, the process must be *logical*. But the simplest-possible logical process for constructing/deriving something would presumably just be a form of logical derivation itself; that is, the process would

Finally, we note that the present model is also a kind of Wheelerian “meaning circuit” [27], in the following way: The sequence of primary displacements in the model springs *from* level 0, the default result of which is basically a smeared-out, meaningless, mess. Observers *within* the system then refer *back* to (the perspective of) level 0 to give the displacements the meanings that we call position, velocity, spin, etc. (as described above), thereby producing the *meaningful* world that we experience.

5.8 The quantum *construction* problem

An underlying theme of this paper is that everything constituting the physical universe is *constructed*, including space and time. A century of quantum mechanics (theory and experiment) echoes this same theme: properties and their values (such as position, velocity, spin, etc.) that were thought to be *there* in the system of interest, needing only to be measured, were actually found to be *constructed* – via unknown mechanisms, but which included *interaction of the system with a “measuring” apparatus*. It follows that “the quantum *measurement* problem” should really be called “the quantum *construction* problem”, and perhaps rephrased as: How are properties such as position, velocity, and spin – and their values – *constructed*?

5.9 A new understanding of wave-particle duality

It has been found experimentally that an object such as an electron exhibits characteristics that are both particle-like and wave-like – the so-called “wave-particle duality”. Under the present model, we can now see roughly how this seemingly paradoxical situation arises.

The basic characteristic of being particle-like is that an object has a definite location in space (i.e., a definite position vector); and the basic characteristic of being wave-like is that an object does *not* have a definite location in space, but is “spread out” across space. We have described above how and why objects have *both* of these characteristics.

First, the \mathbf{d}_0 component of an object is prior to, and thus independent of, ordinary space; so an observer at level 2 or above will, from its own perspective, see that object as being spread out across space (section 4.8). Second, that same observer at level 2 or above can then utilize the perspective of *level 0* to construct a position vector for the object (sections 5.1 and 5.6). Thus, the two principal (and seemingly paradoxical) characteristics of an object that contribute to its wave-particle duality arise from the two main perspectives from which the object is viewed: from the viewpoint of level 2 (or above), and from the viewpoint of level 0. In other words, the principal characteristics of an object’s wave-particle duality are (literally, in the etymological sense) just different *aspects* of the object.

follow the basic form of a logical derivation. QED.

6 Revisiting gravity

Recall our result from section 4.9.4 that (the emission phase of) gravity should be attributed to a *nonforward* displacement of E_1 energy – either backward displacement onto level 0, or lateral/intralevel displacement onto level 1. However, if gravity were attributed to *backward* displacement of E_1 energy onto level 0, then (as concluded in section 5.3) the speed of the graviton would be *infinite*. But gravity actually has a *finite* speed – indeed, all indications are that it propagates at the speed of light, c [28]. Apparently, then, gravity cannot be the result of backward displacement onto level 0, and so it should be the result of *lateral/intralevel* displacement of E_1 energy onto level 1. This means that the graviton is a *level-1* object, with only a \mathbf{d}_0 component, thereby giving it the properties of *relative* position and (due to the lack of a \mathbf{d}_1 component) *absolute* speed. Let us denote the graviton’s \mathbf{d}_0 displacement as $\mathbf{d}_{0,g}$, and denote the genome for the graviton as $\{\mathbf{d}_{0,g}\}$.

Since both E_1 energy and level 1 are independent of \mathbf{d}_1 (section 4.2), then the process of lateral/intralevel displacement of E_1 energy within level 1, as the graviton/ $\{\mathbf{d}_{0,g}\}$, is also independent of \mathbf{d}_1 . (To wit, even if \mathbf{d}_1 and level 2 did not exist, intralevel displacement of E_1 energy within level 1 could *still* occur, obviously without any help from, or dependence upon, \mathbf{d}_1 .) Thus, the graviton/ $\mathbf{d}_{0,g}$ is prior to, and independent of, \mathbf{d}_1 .

In summary, we ascribe the following attributes to the graviton:

- It has only a \mathbf{d}_0 displacement (denoted as $\mathbf{d}_{0,g}$).
- It (i.e. its $\mathbf{d}_{0,g}$ displacement) is *subsequent* to \mathbf{d}_0 .
- It (i.e. its $\mathbf{d}_{0,g}$ displacement) is *prior to*, and thus independent of, \mathbf{d}_1 .
- We therefore have the following order of priority: \mathbf{d}_0 , $\mathbf{d}_{0,g}$, \mathbf{d}_1 .

The last bullet point indicates that, from the perspective of \mathbf{d}_1 , the graviton’s $\mathbf{d}_{0,g}$ displacement will “look” much like the \mathbf{d}_0 displacement; i.e. the graviton/ $\mathbf{d}_{0,g}$ will manifest to \mathbf{d}_1 as a new form of \mathbf{d}_0 , albeit with slightly less priority. Indeed, we might say that $\mathbf{d}_{0,g}$ (the graviton) *mimics* \mathbf{d}_0 .

So, cutting to the chase, our basic theme below is that: \mathbf{d}_1 ’s view of \mathbf{d}_0 *constructs* ordinary space (as usual), and \mathbf{d}_1 ’s view of $\mathbf{d}_{0,g}$ (the graviton) *modifies* that space. Similarly, \mathbf{d}_0 ’s view of \mathbf{d}_1 *constructs* ordinary/classical time (as usual), and $\mathbf{d}_{0,g}$ ’s view of \mathbf{d}_1 *modifies* ordinary time.

That is, the displacement \mathbf{d}_1 will *combine* its views of \mathbf{d}_0 and $\mathbf{d}_{0,g}$ to construct a *resultant* three-dimensional space, which we will denote as $S_{01,r}^3$. So that we may write

$$S_{01,r}^3 = S_{01}^3 + S_{01,g}^3, \quad (5)$$

where S_{01}^3 is the contribution of \mathbf{d}_0 to this resultant space, and $S_{01,g}^3$ is the contribution of the graviton/ $\mathbf{d}_{0,g}$. We already know that \mathbf{d}_0 ’s contribution (S_{01}^3) is just uniform (isotropic, homogeneous), ordinary space. And recall that the uniformity of ordinary space depends on \mathbf{d}_0 *not* having any particular position, direction, or orientation within that space (section 3.4).

A graviton/ $\mathbf{d}_{0,g}$, on the other hand, is a form of \mathbf{d}_0 that *does* have position, direction, and orientation within ordinary space: its *initial* position is the same as the position of the object (e.g. photon, electron or baryon) that emits it; upon emission, the graviton travels in some direction within ordinary space; and it may also have a definite spin. Thus the graviton/ $\mathbf{d}_{0,g}$ is a form of \mathbf{d}_0 that, when viewed from the perspective of \mathbf{d}_1 , will produce a contribution ($S_{01,g}^3$) to the resultant space that is functionally dependent on ordinary space; i.e., a contribution that is *nonuniform* (anisotropic and/or inhomogeneous) – which will in turn make the resultant space nonuniform. Hence, the presence of a graviton/ $\mathbf{d}_{0,g}$ will have the effect of modifying the space that \mathbf{d}_1 (or any object that has a \mathbf{d}_1 component) sees itself as nested/embedded in – changing that space from isotropic and homogeneous S_{01}^3 into anisotropic and inhomogeneous $S_{01,r}^3$.

In addition, recall that the \mathbf{d}_1 displacement, as seen from the perspective of \mathbf{d}_0 , yields ordinary/classical *time* (i.e. S_{10}^1 ; section 3.5). Since the $\mathbf{d}_{0,g}$ displacement of the graviton will have its *own* perspective of \mathbf{d}_1 , then it will produce a contribution to time that may be denoted as $S_{10,g}^1$. Thus, it is proposed that the combination of the perspectives from \mathbf{d}_0 and $\mathbf{d}_{0,g}$ will produce a resultant time, $S_{10,r}^1$, that is *different* from S_{10}^1 . So that we may write

$$S_{10,r}^1 = S_{10}^1 + S_{10,g}^1, \quad (6)$$

where S_{10}^1 is the contribution of \mathbf{d}_0 , and $S_{10,g}^1$ is the contribution of the graviton/ $\mathbf{d}_{0,g}$.

In summary, the view of \mathbf{d}_0 from the perspective of \mathbf{d}_1 yields ordinary (isotropic and homogeneous) three-dimensional space; and the view of \mathbf{d}_1 from the perspective of \mathbf{d}_0 yields ordinary time. The presence of a graviton/ $\mathbf{d}_{0,g}$, viewed from the perspective of \mathbf{d}_1 , then modifies space, making it anisotropic and/or inhomogeneous. Likewise, the view of \mathbf{d}_1 from the perspective of a graviton/ $\mathbf{d}_{0,g}$ modifies time. By these two processes, therefore, the presence of a graviton/ $\mathbf{d}_{0,g}$ alters the geometry of space-time. Indeed, we might say that, due to its place in the order of priority, the graviton/ $\mathbf{d}_{0,g}$ *insinuates* itself into the processes that construct space and time, thereby altering the outputs. The present model, if correct, therefore supplements general relativity by explaining, from first principles, the underlying mechanisms by which energy (actually, E_1 energy) affects space and time.

As an alternative description, we might say that the lateral displacement of E_1 energy (onto level 1), in the form of a graviton/ $\mathbf{d}_{0,g}$, *breaks* the uniformities/symmetries of ordinary space and time. Which echoes a key notion of section 4.9.6: that backward displacements involve symmetries, whereas lateral/intralevel displacements involve *broken* symmetries. To wit, if the graviton were instead the product of *backward* displacement of E_1 energy (onto level 0), then it would *not* have a $\mathbf{d}_{0,g}$ component that mimics \mathbf{d}_0 , and thus would *not* affect or “break” the uniformities of ordinary space and time.

6.1 Example of a gravitational interaction

The results above allow the following description of a gravitational interaction (which may be taken as an update of the one given in section 4.10.4).

Consider an observer A at level 2 or above, i.e. an observer for which the displacements \mathbf{d}_0 and \mathbf{d}_1 are operant. As usual, \mathbf{d}_1 sees \mathbf{d}_0 as ordinary, isotropic, homogeneous, three-dimensional space, S_{01}^3 . Consider also an object/particle B at level 1 or above, having E_1 energy, which emits a graviton in the direction of A . When this graviton arrives at A , it will be processed as follows: from the perspective of its \mathbf{d}_1 component, A will combine the general \mathbf{d}_0 displacement with the graviton's $\mathbf{d}_{0,g}$ displacement to construct a resultant three-dimensional space, $S_{01,r}^3$. In contrast to S_{01}^3 , the directional/positional aspects (within ordinary space) of the graviton's $\mathbf{d}_{0,g}$ displacement will cause the resultant $S_{01,r}^3$ space to be anisotropic and/or inhomogeneous. In addition, A will combine the views of \mathbf{d}_1 from the perspectives of both \mathbf{d}_0 and $\mathbf{d}_{0,g}$, thereby transforming from the ordinary time S_{10}^1 to the *altered* time $S_{10,r}^1$. That is, the presence of the graviton emitted by B will alter the geometry of space-time as seen by A .

7 Conclusion

From six simple postulates we have managed to provide basic explanations for, or derivations of, many hitherto unexplained physical phenomena: the (3+1)-dimensionality of space and time; fundamental symmetries; inflation (its beginning and ending); dark energy; the construction of position, velocity, and spin properties; etc. In addition, as quantum physics seems to demand, the model elevates observation and observers (of many kinds) to key roles in constructing the world, and provides a mechanism for instantaneous communication/influence across all of space, by which the values of particle properties may be correlated.

Chemistry was explained a century ago by the discovery of a discrete action (h) that constructs a sequence of discrete energy levels in atoms. Similarly, if the present model is basically correct, then *physics* might be explained by the discovery of discrete fundamental displacements that construct a sequence of discrete levels.

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